

THE LONDON SCHOOL
OF ECONOMICS AND
POLITICAL SCIENCE

UNIVERSIT
OF TARTU

UNIVERSITY OF HELSINKI

Rethinking Media Literacy and Digital Skills (REMEDIIS) TOOLKIT

The REMEDIIS consortium includes **seven academic partners** and **14 non-academic cooperation partners**.

REMEDIS Toolkit Structure

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Section 1: Introduction

Understanding REMEDIS & its Toolkit

The **REMEDIS Toolkit** is designed to empower educators, policymakers, and civil society organisations with practical resources to enhance **media literacy and digital skills** across diverse communities. Developed within the **REMEDIS project**, this toolkit provides research-based strategies, intervention models, and evaluation frameworks to foster **critical engagement with digital media, combat misinformation, and promote responsible online participation.**

Introducing REMEDIS

The REMEDIS project is funded by the EU's CHANSE (Collaboration of Humanities and Social Sciences in Europe) programme.

The project has **two main goals:**

1. REMEDIS aims to create and assess ways to build media literacy and digital skills (ML&DS) and understand their positive impacts in different areas of life.
2. REMEDIS aims to find and measure key factors for ML&DS at all ages and to assess how effective current ML&DS interventions are at reaching positive outcomes for participants.

Defining Media Literacy & Digital Skills (ML&DS)

Media literacy and digital skills are related concepts, but they focus on different aspects of interacting with technology, media, and information

Media literacy: The ability to critically analyse, evaluate, create, and engage with media content in various forms (e.g., *understanding how media content is created; recognising biases, perspectives, and underlying agendas; assessing credibility and reliability*).

Digital skills: The abilities required to use digital devices, applications, and tools safely and effectively. *For example: Operating digital devices like computers, tablets, and smartphones; navigating software and platforms; using advanced tools like coding or digital design applications; ensuring cybersecurity*

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Both competencies are essential for individuals to participate meaningfully in society, make informed decisions, and safeguard against misinformation and digital threats.

REMEDIS Target Groups & Their Caregivers

REMEDIS places a **special focus** on the value of ML&DS interventions for the following target groups:

- *Disadvantaged youth (NEETs - Not in Education, Employment, or Training)*
- *The unemployed*
- *Refugees*
- *People with lower socio-economic status (SES)*
- *Carers of NEET youth*
- *(Future) teachers*

REMEDIS: Aim & Objectives

The **overarching aim** of REMEDIS is to understand what the impacts of ML&DS interventions in the different life domains are in terms of positive outcomes.

To this end, the project has **four objectives**:

1. To improve existing theoretical knowledge about the actual outcomes of interventions
2. To improve and to enhance existing media literacy and digital skills intervention strategies based on existing and emerging evidence
3. To adopt advanced methods, to develop and to validate instruments for evaluating intervention strategies
4. To produce evidence-based policy recommendations and to develop a user-friendly, customisable evaluation toolkit

The Importance of ML&DS

In today's digital society, media literacy and digital skills are essential in different life domains.

Critical thinking
& informed
decision making

Effective
communication

Civic
engagement

Economic
opportunities

Personal
Security &
privacy

Adaptation to
technological
changes

Cultural &
social awareness

Critical Thinking & Informed Decision Making

Media literacy and digital skills help people to navigate and evaluate the large amounts of information that we are exposed to everyday, by enabling us to think critically about information and to make informed decisions.

Critical thinking: ML&DS help people figure out what information they can trust. They teach us how to spot reliable sources, avoid fake news, and understand when information might be misleading. This is especially important when scrolling through social media or reading news online.

Informed decision making: ML&DS help people make better choices in important areas like health, money, and politics. For example, ML&DS can help someone decide if health advice they find online is accurate, if a financial offer is real, or if a political claim is true.

Effective Communication

Media literacy and digital skills (ML&DS) help people communicate clearly and effectively by creating accurate and engaging digital messages, and they empower individuals to create engaging content that resonates with their audience.

Digital interaction: ML&DS enable effective communication across a wide range of online platforms, including social media, professional networks, and collaboration tools. These platforms provide opportunities to connect with others, share ideas, and engage in meaningful conversations, whether for personal, educational, or professional purposes.

Content creation: Understanding how to use digital tools allows individuals to create, share, and distribute content in a responsible and impactful way. From designing visually appealing presentations to producing engaging videos or writing thoughtful blog posts, ML&DS help ensure messages are clear, relevant, and tailored to the intended audience.

Civic Engagement

Media literacy and digital skills (ML&DS) are important for civic engagement as they empower people to make informed decisions about social and political issues, and to actively participate in public discourse, advocate for causes, and collaborate on digital platforms to drive social change.

Political participation: ML&DS empower citizens to engage in the democratic process by helping them analyse political messages, campaigns, and policies. ML&DS enable people to recognise biases, fact-check claims, and make informed choices that reflect their values and priorities.

Social movements: ML&DS facilitate participation in social movements and advocacy. They enable individuals to use online tools and platforms to mobilise supporters, organise events, and amplify their voices on a global scale.

Economic Opportunities

Media literacy and digital skills (ML&DS) are essential for economic opportunities, as they equip individuals with the ability to use digital tools and platforms critical for most modern jobs. They empower entrepreneurs and professionals to market their skills, grow businesses, and adapt to a rapidly changing economy through continuous learning and innovation.

Job market: Many jobs today require digital proficiency, and strong digital skills can expand the range of employment opportunities. Skills like using software, specialised tools like data analysis programmes, or content management systems make candidates more competitive in the job market.

Entrepreneurship: ML&DS support entrepreneurial endeavours, enabling people to leverage online marketing, e-commerce, and social media platforms to grow their businesses. Entrepreneurs can use ML&DS to design professional websites, reach broader audiences, and manage operations efficiently, helping them compete effectively in the global economy.

Personal Security & Online Safety

Media literacy and digital skills (ML&DS) are crucial for personal security and online safety, as they help individuals recognise online threats such as phishing scams and fake websites. They also empower users to protect their personal information by managing privacy settings, creating strong passwords, and understanding best practices in cybersecurity.

Online safety: Understanding digital security helps protect personal information from cyber threats (such as identity theft, hacking, and online scams) and control online presence, advertising preferences, location settings, age permissions, and data control.

Privacy management: Media literacy includes knowledge and skills about managing digital footprints and maintaining privacy online.

Adaptation to Technological Changes

Media literacy and digital skills (ML&DS) are essential for adapting to technological changes, as they enable individuals to learn new tools, platforms, and technologies quickly and effectively.

Remaining digitally literate in a changing landscape: As technology evolves, ML&DS enable people to understand and adapt to new tools, platforms, and innovations. They ensure that people can navigate emerging technologies confidently, helping them stay relevant and effective in an increasingly digital world, whether in their personal, educational, or professional lives.

Lifelong learning: ML&DS cultivate a mindset of continuous learning, which is essential for keeping up with technological advancements. By encouraging curiosity and the ability to evaluate and integrate new knowledge, these skills empower individuals to embrace change, explore new opportunities, and thrive in a world where technology is constantly reshaping how we live and work.

Cultural & Social Awareness

Media literacy and digital skills (ML&DS) enhance cultural and social awareness by helping individuals critically analyse media representations and understand diverse perspectives. They also enable people to connect with others globally, fostering empathy and meaningful dialogue across different cultures and communities.

Diverse perspectives: ML&DS play a vital role in fostering an understanding of diverse perspectives and cultures by teaching individuals how to critically analyse media representations. This awareness promotes empathy, challenges stereotypes, and reduces biases.

Global connectivity: ML&DS make it possible to connect with people from all corners of the globe, expanding social networks and deepening cultural understanding. Online, individuals can engage in meaningful conversations, collaborate on shared interests, and learn from experiences outside their immediate environment.

Media Literacy & Digital Skills Intervention Context

Environmental external factors

(geography/material environment; digital environment; political, economic and cultural landscape)

Organisational resources

- Human resources (professionals, volunteers, training, skills, payment/contracting)
- Financial resources (source of funding, project or organisation based funding, sustainability)
- Physical resources (facilities, offices, acces to mass media or outreach channels)
- Dedicated intervention resources (Equipment, devices, licenses, subscriptions used)

Stakeholders (influence on design and evaluation)

- Funding (public, private, non-profit, mixed partnership)
- Providers (teachers, volunteers or intermediaries)
- Beneficiaries
- Partners
- Other actors

Intervention

Format

- online, face-to-face
- Costs
- Length
- Formal/informal

Content

- Target Group (beneficiaries/community)
- Type of literacy
- Other content

Aims/outcomes

- Economic/educational
- Civic/participatory
- Well-being
- Certification

Media Literacy & Digital Skills Interventions

Media Literacy & Digital Skills (ML&DS) interventions are programmes or strategies designed to enhance individuals' abilities to critically analyse media content and effectively use digital technologies. These interventions aim to improve knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for navigating the media landscape and digital world.

Media literacy interventions focus on teaching individuals how to understand, analyse, and evaluate media content critically.

Digital skills interventions aim to improve individuals' ability to effectively and safely use digital technologies.

Media Literacy (ML) Interventions Typically Cover:

1. Media formats and platforms
2. Critical analysis of (social) media content
3. Misinformation, disinformation, and fake news
4. Media influence
5. Education and career development
6. Well-being
7. Informed consumer choices
8. Ethical media consumption

1. Media Formats & Platforms

ML interventions can contribute to people's understanding of the various media formats and platforms, each with their unique characteristics, mechanisms, applications, and goals.

Media formats and platforms include:

Print media: Traditional formats like newspapers, magazines, and books, ideal for in-depth analysis with longer publication cycles.

Digital media: Internet-based content, such as news sites and blogs, offering real-time updates and interactive engagement.

Broadcast media: Television and radio, reach large audiences with impactful audio-visual content in news and entertainment.

Social media: Platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram enable direct communication and influence both personal and public discourse.

2. Critical Analysis of (Social) Media Content

ML interventions can teach people the knowledge and skills they require to engage thoughtfully with media and to critically reflect on the (social) media content they encounter.

Critical analysis skills involve learning how to carefully examine media messages.

This includes understanding the content, context, and purpose of the information presented: for example, identifying biases and agendas within media or evaluating the credibility of sources.

3. Misinformation, Disinformation & Fake News

ML interventions can address topics relating to misinformation and disinformation, equipping participants with the relevant knowledge and skills to **distinguish between trustworthy and misleading information**.

Interventions could teach heuristic and systematic strategies, and their strengths and limitations.

Additionally, relevant knowledge could relate to the use of **sensational headlines, emotional appeals**, and **confirmation bias** in misinformation and disinformation, with the goal of manipulating public opinion.

4. Media Influence

Media have a powerful influence on our **perceptions, attitudes**, and **behaviours**, shaping how we see ourselves, others, and the world around us.

ML interventions are essential in helping us understand these dynamics by exploring how media influences societal issues such as **body image, consumer behaviour**, and **political opinions**. As such, interventions empower people to recognise the subtle and overt ways media affect their thoughts and decisions.

Recognising media's pervasive influence allows people to critically engage with content, question underlying messages, and develop a more nuanced perspective.

5. Education & Career Development

ML interventions can play a role in strengthening the knowledge and skills that are relevant for successful outcomes in education or furthering one's career.

Education development: These interventions enhance research skills, improve digital communication, and teach individuals how to create and share content responsibly.

Career development: Being able to effectively navigate and use various digital platforms (such as email, video conferencing tools, and social media) enhances workplace efficiency and productivity. Understanding how to responsibly create and share content is crucial, as it involves maintaining professionalism online, protecting intellectual property, and respecting digital ethics.

6. Well-Being

ML interventions can cover various topics relating to online and offline well-being:

Balanced media consumption: Encouraging positive media engagement while reducing exposure to harmful content.

Mental health impact: Helping curate social media feeds for positivity, reducing anxiety and depression risks.

Digital detox: Promoting screen-free breaks to prevent stress and burnout, offering practical tools for balance.

Recognising harmful content: Enhancing skills to identify and avoid clickbait and misinformation for informed media choices.

7. Informed Consumer Choices

ML interventions can contribute to people's advertising literacy:

Recognising persuasive tactics: ML interventions can help develop skills to identify advertising intent and resist manipulative marketing.

Emotional appeals: ML interventions can help recognise emotional triggers in ads, such as family imagery used to drive sales.

Product placement: ML interventions can help raise people's awareness of subtle brand integrations as a marketing strategy.

Influencer endorsements: ML interventions can help distinguish between genuine recommendations and paid promotions.

8. Ethical Media Consumption

ML interventions can contribute to people's awareness of their ethical media consumption. By highlighting the principles of **respect, responsibility, and truthfulness**, interventions focusing on ethical media consumption can foster a respectful media environment in which users understand their responsibilities in creating and sharing media contents.

Ethical media consumption interventions could for instance focus on **copyright awareness** and users' respect of intellectual property rights to avoid legal issues and support creators of original content. By focusing on **trustworthiness and reliability**, ML interventions could support people in avoiding misinformation by promoting fact-checking skills and reflection about spreading potentially false information.

ML interventions could also focus on interpersonal communication by promoting **respectful online interactions**. By equipping people with skills to prevent cyberbullying, trolling, and hate speech, interventions could promote positive and constructive online behaviour.

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Digital Skills (DS) Interventions Typically Cover:

1. Fact-checking
2. Media bias analysis
3. Online communication
4. Digital content creation & ethics
5. Digital footprint awareness
6. Cybersecurity and online safety
7. Advanced digital skills (for specific needs)
8. Problem-solving and troubleshooting

1. Fact-Checking

Digital skills are essential for ensuring people can identify accurate information and avoid spreading misinformation. Fact-checking empowers individuals to verify the credibility of information before trusting or sharing it.

Evaluating information: DS interventions can teach individuals how to assess the credibility of sources and identify red flags in false or misleading content. Interventions can improve people's skills for verifying sources, cross-referencing information, or reverse image search.

Critical mindset: Fact-checking training equips individuals with the skills to navigate the overwhelming flow of online information with a critical mindset. It helps combat the spread of fake news and promotes more trustworthy online interactions.

2. Media Bias Analysis

Digital skills are crucial for understanding how bias shapes media narratives and influences perceptions. Recognising media bias allows individuals to consume content more critically and form balanced opinions.

Analysing bias: DS interventions can help participants identify different types of media bias, such as political, cultural, or commercial bias.

Assessing credibility: By learning to detect bias in language, tone, and framing, interventions can teach participants to better assess the credibility of media contents and engage with a more nuanced understanding of complex issues.

3. Online Communication

DS interventions can greatly enhance people's ability to communicate effectively and respectfully online, leading to better personal and professional connections.

Effective messaging: In DS interventions, participants learn to tailor their tone, language, and style to different platforms, such as professional emails, social media, or instant messaging apps. They also explore the importance of netiquette in maintaining positive online interactions.

Practical applications: DS interventions focusing on online communication can include crafting concise emails, resolving conflicts respectfully, and collaborating effectively in digital workspaces.

4. Digital Content Creation & Ethics

DS interventions for digital content creation can empower participants to share ideas and engage audiences, while focusing on how it can be done responsibly and ethically. Digital skills ensure that content is accurate, inclusive, and respectful of copyright laws.

Creating responsibly: DS interventions can teach participants to use creative software and tools to produce engaging and professional content. Workshops can also cover important related topics such as copyright, plagiarism, and ethical considerations in content creation.

Gaining hands-on experience: Through hands-on projects in DS interventions, participants gain experience creating blogs, social media posts, or videos that align with ethical standards, building both technical and creative confidence.

5. Digital Footprint Awareness

DS interventions enhance digital footprint awareness by equipping participants with skills to manage their online presence, highlighting its impact on personal and professional opportunities.

Managing online presence: DS interventions teach participants how to audit their digital footprint, review privacy settings, and make conscious decisions about the information they share online.

Identifying risks: Interventions can encourage self-audits by having participants ‘google’ themselves, identify risks, and adjust their online presence to align with their values and goals.

6. Cybersecurity & Online Safety

Digital skills protect individuals from online threats like scams, phishing, and identity theft. DS interventions can provide participants with the knowledge they need to safeguard personal information and navigate the internet securely.

Staying safe online: DS interventions can tackle topics such as recognising phishing attempts, creating strong passwords, and enabling two-factor authentication. They can also explore how to identify secure websites and avoid risky downloads.

Cybersecurity scenarios: DS interventions can provide training with important real-world scenarios, such as spotting a phishing email or securing a personal device, to build practical cybersecurity skills.

7. Advanced Digital Skills (for Specific Needs)

Advanced digital skills open doors to specialised opportunities in personal and professional life. These include technical skills like coding, data analysis, and graphic design.

Building expertise: DS interventions can introduce participants to advanced tools and platforms like Python, Excel, or Adobe Creative Suite, aligning their training with specific career or personal development goals.

Advanced training projects: By offering targeted training, mentorship, or project-based learning, DS interventions can help participants develop expertise in advanced areas like programming, data visualisation, or multimedia production.

8. Problem Solving & Troubleshooting

DS interventions can empower individuals to resolve common tech challenges efficiently, building confidence and independence in navigating digital tools.

Effective problem solving: In DS interventions, participants learn structured approaches to troubleshooting, such as identifying issues, researching solutions, and testing fixes.

Troubleshooting: DS training involves solving real-world problems, like fixing connectivity issues or resolving software errors, to prepare participants for everyday digital challenges.

Importance of Evaluating ML&DS Interventions

Evaluating the effectiveness of ML&DS interventions is valuable for several reasons:

- Evaluations ensure **effectiveness**: They confirm that envisioned goals are met and that interventions stay relevant in relation to real-world needs.
- Evaluations support the **optimisation of resources**: Evaluation outcomes can contribute to an effective allocation of resources to maximise the impact of the intervention.
- Evaluations demonstrate **value**: Evaluation outcomes build trust and accountability with stakeholders.
- Evaluations support **funding**: Proven success attracts future funding and advocacy.
- Evaluations inform **future intervention programmes**: Evaluation outcomes can be helpful in guiding the design of impactful future initiatives.
- Evaluations boost **engagement**: Outcomes are helpful in tailoring interventions to participant needs.
- Evaluations **advance field knowledge**: They contribute insights to the field of ML&DS research.

Challenges Associated with ML&DS Intervention Evaluation

Defining Clear Metrics & Outcomes

The challenge

Establishing measurable outcomes for ML&DS intervention evaluations is challenging due to the dynamic nature of these skills. Programmes often struggle to determine what success looks like and how to quantify improvements in areas like critical thinking or content evaluation.

Key considerations

Clear, actionable goals, such as the ability to fact-check or identify bias, must be defined alongside appropriate metrics to evaluate progress effectively. A focus on measurable skills and behaviours ensures more targeted and impactful outcomes.

Assessment Tools & Methods

The challenge

Choosing the right tools and methods to assess participant progress is a complex task. ML&DS interventions often involve subjective estimations of skills.

Key considerations

Reliable assessments, such as performance tests or practical evaluations, can help measure these skills accurately. Using both pre- and post-intervention assessments ensures a clearer understanding of programme impact and participants' development.

Participant Variability

The challenge

Intervention participants come from diverse backgrounds with varying levels of knowledge, skills, and learning preferences. This variability makes it difficult to design a one-size-fits-all programme or a robust evaluation strategy.

Key considerations

Effective interventions must be flexible, offering tailored content, adaptive pacing, and support that address individual needs. Ensuring inclusivity and accessibility is essential for engaging all participants and maximising learning outcomes. Taking into account this variability in needs and learning styles is key for nuanced evaluation.

Longitudinal Tracking

The challenge

Evaluating the long-term impact of ML&DS interventions presents unique challenges, as skills retention and application may diminish over time. Tracking participants after the programme ends can be complicated and requires additional resources and planning.

Key considerations

Regular follow-up assessments and surveys can provide valuable insights into how participants use and sustain their new skills in real-world scenarios over months or years. Longitudinal data help refine interventions and assess their lasting value.

Contextual Factors

The challenge

Cultural, social, and technological factors heavily influence how participants interact with and apply skills gained in ML&DS interventions. For example, access to technology, societal norms, and local media landscapes can shape engagement and learning.

Key considerations

Programmes must take these factors into account when designing ML&DS intervention evaluations, ensuring the evaluation is relevant, adaptable, and practical within the participants' unique contexts. Customising programmes to fit these factors improves accessibility and effectiveness.

Resource Constraints

The challenge

Limited resources, including funding and time, often restrict the scope and scalability of ML&DS intervention evaluations. These constraints can impact the quality and reach of programmes, especially in under-resourced areas.

Key considerations

Leveraging cost-effective solutions, such as open-source tools, online platforms, and partnerships with community organisations, can help maximise impact while minimising expenses.

Estimating Resources for Evaluation Implementation (1/3)

Human resources include evaluation experts to design and execute assessments, programme staff to deliver training and manage operations, and support staff for logistical and administrative tasks.

Financial resources are essential, with funding needed to support activities and outreach, while effective budget planning ensures resources are used efficiently.

Technological resources play a vital role, including data collection tools for gathering feedback, data management systems for securely organising information, and analysis software to evaluate programme impact.

Estimating Resources for Evaluation Implementation (2/3)

Educational resources include training materials and instructional guides to support effective delivery of the programme and ensure participants receive high-quality, structured learning experiences.

Physical resources are necessary to facilitate programme evaluation operations, such as office space for administrative tasks and equipment like computers, projectors, and other tools needed for training sessions.

Data collection resources are critical for measuring programme outcomes, including well-designed instruments to gather information and a robust sampling framework to ensure data are representative and reliable.

Estimating Resources for Evaluation Implementation (3/3)

Participant engagement resources include incentives to motivate participation and communication channels, such as email, messaging platforms, or social media, to keep participants informed and connected throughout the programme.

Ethical and legal resources ensure the evaluation is conducted responsibly, including ethical guidelines to safeguard participant rights and privacy, and adherence to legal compliance requirements to meet local and international standards.

Reporting and dissemination resources are crucial for sharing outcomes and driving improvements. These include report writing to document findings, publication channels to share results with stakeholders, and feedback mechanisms to gather insights for refining future interventions.

Ethical Considerations

The challenge

ML&DS intervention evaluations must navigate important ethical concerns, such as participant privacy, data protection, and equitable access. Collecting and managing personal data from participants requires transparency and adherence to ethical guidelines.

Key considerations

Programmes should ensure content and delivery methods are free from bias and promote fairness. Respecting participants' rights and diverse backgrounds throughout the process builds trust and ensures ethical integrity.

Impact Attributions

The challenge

Determining the specific impact of an ML&DS intervention can be difficult when multiple factors influence participants' skills and behaviours. For example, exposure to other training, media, or experiences may also contribute to observed changes.

Key considerations

Using control groups, mixed-methods evaluations, and direct participant feedback can help isolate and understand the unique effects of the intervention. Careful attribution ensures a more accurate evaluation of programme success.

Partnering with Organisations for Complex Project Implementation

Implementing an ML&DS intervention often requires collaboration with multiple organisations to maximise effectiveness. Collaborations with diverse stakeholders enhance projects by combining **strengths, resources, and expertise**, offering varied perspectives, access to specialised tools, and broader reach.

For example, a digital skills project for disadvantaged youth might involve a **community centre** offering a safe training space, a **nonprofit** developing a tailored curriculum, and a **technology company** donating laptops and internet access.

Further Reading & Resources

Further Reading

- Potter, J. (2021). Media Literacy. SAGE Inc
- d’Haenens, L., Vissenberg, J., Puusepp, M., Edisherashvili, N., Martinez-Castro, D., Helsper, E. J., et al (2025). Fostering media literacy: a systematic evidence review of intervention effectiveness for diverse target groups. *Media and Communication*, 13.
<https://doi.org/10.17645/mac.8901>
- Chaiken, S. (1980). Heuristic versus systematic information processing and the use of source versus message cues in persuasion. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 39(5), 752-766.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.39.5.752>

Resources

- [Think Critically, Click Wisely \(Unesco, 2021\)](#)
- [Coping Strategies Against Information Disorder](#)
- [Toolbox of individual-level interventions against online misinformationMedia Education Lab](#)

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Section 2: Laying the Groundwork

How do You Plan the Evaluation?

In this section, we will explore the core elements of effective intervention evaluation. From understanding guiding principles and defining the purpose, to building a *Theory of Change* and developing evaluation frameworks, you will gain insights into setting baselines, measuring outcomes, and aligning key indicators. We'll also address securing resources, assessing quality, and meeting standards to ensure impactful evaluations.

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Start Smart: Nine Key Principles for Media Literacy Intervention Evaluation

Start with these principles
in mind

1. Holistic approach: Evaluate media literacy initiatives across key areas like critical thinking, civic engagement, and social inclusion.

2. Contextual relevance: Assess initiatives within the specific socio-cultural, political, and technological contexts to ensure they address relevant issues and meet the diverse needs of different populations.

3. Evidence-based practices: Use rigorous research and evidence, including both quantitative and qualitative data, to measure the effectiveness of media literacy interventions and guide future strategies.

4. Long-term impact: When possible, consider the long-term impact of media literacy efforts on individuals, communities, and society, looking beyond short-term outcomes like knowledge gains or behaviour changes.

Nine Principles

5. Stakeholder engagement: Engage stakeholders from government, academia, civil society, the media industry, and other relevant sectors to ensure a collaborative approach and an accountable evaluation process.

6. Adaptability and innovation: Evaluate initiatives for their adaptability to changing media landscapes and emerging technologies, and their capacity for innovative solutions to new challenges.

7. Ethical considerations: Ensure initiatives adhere to ethical standards, respecting privacy principles, data protection, freedom of expression, and cultural sensitivity.

8. Sustainability: Evaluate the long-term viability of media literacy initiatives in terms of funding, institutional support, partnerships, and community engagement to ensure continued impact.

9. Transparency and accountability: Ensure transparency in the evaluation process with clear criteria, methodologies, and reporting, to foster accountability and learning from both successes and challenges.

These guidelines help evaluate media literacy initiatives and support. However, not every tip fits every situation—smaller projects may not need impact evaluations or government involvement.

Use your judgment to adapt, based on your context and needs.

Define the Evaluation Purpose & Focus

Define the *problem* your intervention is targeting and the *evaluation purpose*

What problem is your intervention solving?

Problem:

In-service teachers struggle to identify misinformation and help students critically assess online content, leading to the spread of unreliable information in classrooms.

What exactly are you trying to Evaluate?

Evaluation Purpose:

Assess whether the intervention significantly improves teachers' ability to accurately identify misinformation and effectively integrate media literacy skills into their lesson plans and classroom activities.

The Journey or the destination: Do you want to evaluate the *process* or the *outcomes*?

What is the focus of your intervention?

Process evaluation example:

You assess how the media literacy training was delivered to teachers. This includes examining whether the materials were presented clearly, if the sessions were interactive, and if teachers were engaged throughout the training.

Outcomes evaluation example:

You measure the results of a media literacy training. For example, you check whether teachers can now better identify misinformation and apply media literacy skills in their classrooms.

Both matter—one tracks the journey, the other checks the results. It all depends on your needs!

Intervention Outcome Evaluation: Chasing Impact or Settling for Outcomes?

Impact evaluation: prerequisites

- **Control/comparison group:** To isolate the intervention's effect.
- **Baseline data:** Pre-intervention data to track changes over time.
- **Robust data collection:** Systematic and reliable methods.
- **Time & resources:** Impact evaluation needs more budget, time & expertise.
- **Causal pathway:** Clear link between the intervention & the outcome.
- **Strong scientific expertise:** researchers who can implement rigorous studies

Intervention Outcome Evaluation: Chasing Impact or Settling for Outcomes?

Outcome evaluation: when impact cannot be measured

- **No control group:** You cannot compare against a non-intervention group.
- **Limited data:** Baseline data or detailed tracking is not available.
- **Short-term focus:** Measuring immediate results, not long-term changes.
- **Resource constraints:** Lack of time, budget, or expertise for in-depth analysis.
- **Complex environments:** Too many factors to attribute change solely to the intervention.

[See more in Section II](#)

Identify the *Baseline*: Know Where You Stand to Measure What You Build!

Before you can measure how far you've come, you need to know where you started.

Establishing the baseline is like setting the starting line in a race—you cannot celebrate your progress without knowing your initial speed!

Why it matters: The baseline gives you something to compare the intervention's success against. Without it, how do you know what has changed?

How to do it: Collect data on key indicators before the intervention begins, whether through surveys, assessments, or observations. This will be your reference point to track growth and improvements over time

Identify the *Baseline*: Know Where You Stand to Measure What You Build!

Why it is essential: In more rigorous studies (like impact evaluations), establishing a baseline is crucial for accurately tracking progress and measuring success. For example, in a media literacy intervention, a baseline helps determine how much participants' skills have improved by the end of the programme.

When it is not needed: In smaller, less formal studies or outcome evaluations, a baseline may not be necessary. For instance, if you are only interested in observing short-term results or immediate feedback from participants, a baseline might not provide added value.

Building the Basics: *What Exactly Is a Theory of Change?*

What is a Theory of Change (ToC)?

A *Theory of Change (ToC)*, also known as a Logic Model, outlines the logic behind how an intervention will lead to the desired change. It articulates the reasoning for each step and demonstrates the cause-and-effect relationships between the components of the intervention implementation process leading to final outcome of the intervention – solving the ‘Problem’ that the Intervention targets.

What ToC Does: Key Points

Logic of change: the **ToC** outlines the logic behind an intervention, illustrating how specific activities generate concrete outputs, lead to short-term outcomes, and contribute to long-term change, ultimately achieving the intended impact.

Assumptions: It highlights the assumptions underlying the Intervention implementation plan, such as external conditions or factors necessary for change to occur.

Pathway to impact: The **ToC** maps the path from the initial problem to the final impact or outcome, outlining intermediate steps, such as resources, activities, and outputs.

Theory of Change: Its Importance for Intervention Evaluation

Why is ToC needed for Intervention evaluation?

By clearly outlining the logic, assumptions, and pathways, the **ToC** provides a structured approach for understanding, implementing, and evaluating interventions.

It is especially vital during evaluation, as it allows evaluators to determine whether outcomes match the original goals set during the design phase. By linking specific activities—such as training, policy reforms, or outreach—to expected results, it helps evaluators track progress, identify what is working, and understand why. This keeps evaluations focused, enables clearer comparisons between predicted and actual outcomes, and helps attribute success or failure to specific elements.

Without a **ToC**, evaluations risk losing clarity and may miss key opportunities to fully understand the intervention's impact.

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Application of a ToC Example:

If an intervention is designed to improve digital literacy among NEET youth, the **ToC** will:

- Define the problem (NEET youth lacking digital skills),
- Map out the required inputs (e.g., trainers, curriculum),
- Define activities leading to outputs (e.g., hands-on training in essential digital tools and job search skills)
- Show the expected outputs (e.g., participants' complete digital literacy courses)
- Outline short-term outcomes (e.g., improved digital proficiency)
- Highlight long-term impact (e.g., better employment prospects)

See sample of completed **ToC evaluation frameworks [HERE](#).**

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Turning Theory into Action: Building an Evaluation Framework

The Evaluation Framework is based on your *Theory of Change*. In addition to detailing **ToC** components—*inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impact*—the following elements will support evaluation planning:

- Identifying of the potential *target audience* and the human resources needed for implementation
- Identifying the necessary *data and sources* for each evaluation stage
- Selecting *methods for data collection*
- Assessing *risks* at each stage

By completing *the Evaluation Framework*, you are creating a comprehensive evaluation plan that offers solid insights into the success of your intervention, helping measure and understand its impact.

Various templates of *Evaluation Frameworks* are available [here](#)—choose and adapt one that suits your intervention evaluation needs.

Theory of change:

Process Evaluation

Assess if programme was implemented as designed

Impact Evaluation

Assess if programme achieved goals

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Turning Theory into Action: Considering Barriers & Drivers

Factoring in Drivers & Barriers in Evaluation Planning

When planning an evaluation, it is essential to think about both the **drivers**—those factors that will push the intervention forward—and the **barriers**—the potential obstacles that could slow it down. By integrating these into your evaluation framework, you can create a more realistic and adaptable plan.

Why does this matter? Because knowing what is helping and what is hindering your intervention allows you to make adjustments early, ensuring that your evaluation stays on track and delivers meaningful insights.

While media literacy intervention implementation has its own drivers and barriers, the evaluation process is also shaped by various factors. Below are examples of **evaluation-specific drivers** (e.g., strong stakeholder engagement, adequate funding) and **barriers** (e.g., limited expertise, data access challenges). Consider your specific context to identify the most relevant drivers and barriers for your evaluation.

Possible Barriers & Drivers for Intervention Evaluation

Barriers:

Organisational barriers:

- **Lack of expertise:** Limited staff with skills in evaluation design and implementation.
- **Budget constraints:** Insufficient funds to conduct a thorough evaluation.
- **Data challenges:** Difficulty in collecting and managing relevant data.
- **Internal resistance:** Resistance to adopting new evaluation approaches.

External barriers:

- **Low engagement:** Target groups may lack time, interest, or trust in the intervention.
- **Access issues:** Limited access to necessary technology or resources.
- **Privacy concerns:** Legal or ethical issues around data collection.
- **Cultural resistance:** Skepticism or resistance to the intervention's focus.

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Possible Barriers & Drivers for Intervention Evaluation

Drivers:

Organisational drivers:

- **Leadership support:** Strong backing from organisational leadership.
- **Established networks:** Use of existing relationships with partners or stakeholders.
- **Internal expertise:** Staff with experience in programme evaluation.

External drivers:

- **Participant motivation:** Strong interest from target groups to engage with the intervention.
- **Partnerships:** Collaborations with external experts or research institutions.
- **Funding opportunities:** Availability of grants or external funding.
- **Community support:** Support from local organisations or influential groups.

Securing Funding & Building Evaluation Capacity

When your evaluation becomes resource-heavy or requires expertise beyond your team's capabilities, it is time to get strategic. First, make sure you have mapped out the financial and human resources you will need.

If you find gaps in specialised research expertise, consider partnering with external experts or [research institutions](#) to fill those knowledge gaps and ensure a thorough evaluation.

At the same time, don't forget to explore funding options—grants from [government agencies, foundations, or international organisations](#) can provide the boost you need to see the evaluation through successfully.

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Backward Planning: Defining & Understanding Intervention Outcomes

Backward Planning: Understanding Outcomes

What is an outcome?

Changes expected after an intervention.

Outcome Levels:

- **Individual:** Personal growth or behavioral changes.
- **Policy:** Shifts in organizational or governmental rules.
- **Societal Impact:** Broad, long-term societal changes.

Key Distinctions:

- **Outcome ≠ Outputs:** Outputs are the steps, outcomes are the end results.

Types of Outcomes:

- **Short-term:** Immediate, tangible effects.
- **Long-term:** Sustained changes over time.
- **Impact:** Broad, lasting societal changes

Example Outcome:

NEET youth gain critical skills to assess online job resources, leading to more informed career and education choices.

[Here](#) is the bank of Media Literacy Outcomes you can choose from. Consider your Intervention goals when selecting.

Measuring Success: Uncovering Key Indicators for Outcomes

What is a Key Performance indicator? (KPI):

a *measurable* variable used to assess progress toward achieving specific goals or outcomes.

Example: A KPI for a programme aimed at improving elderly well-being could be *the percentage of elderly participants reporting increased social interaction* after attending community events.

[In this Outcomes Bank](#) you can choose possible ML Intervention outcomes, their indicator(s) and matching example survey items that you can use or adapt to collect your data (Ofcom, 2024).

Key Performance Indicators (KPI) can target different aspects of an individual's development.

K Knowledge
I Behaviour
I Awareness
S Perception

Fully measuring an outcome often requires considering multiple KPIs, to capture different dimensions of impact.

Example: evaluating a teacher's ability to create and manage online content might involve a behaviour-related indicator, such as the frequency of online content sharing, and a knowledge-related indicator, such as demonstrated knowledge of content creation.

Illustrative Framework for Aligning Outcomes, Indicators & Measures

The Illustrative Intervention **Outcome** Evaluation Framework below breaks down outcomes into **Knowledge, Skills, Attitudes & Behaviour**, aligning each with **indicators & assessment tools**.

1. Knowledge

Outcomes: Increased understanding of media landscapes, digital technologies, and information literacy concepts.

KPIs:

- % increase in correct responses between pre- and post-tests.

Assessment Measures:

- Pre- and post-tests evaluating participants' understanding of key concepts.

2. Skill

Outcomes: improved critical thinking, digital literacy, media production, and communication capabilities.

KPIs:

- Average score increase on portfolio assessments.
- % of participants achieving proficiency benchmarks on critical thinking rubrics.

Assessment Measures:

- Portfolios to evaluate content creation skills (e.g., video editing, graphic design).
- Rubric-based evaluations of critical thinking in written or group work.

Note: Matching outcomes with the right indicators and measurements is key to effective evaluation

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Illustrative Framework for Aligning Outcomes, Indicators & Measures

3. Attitudes

Outcomes: Positive shifts in participants' attitudes toward responsible media consumption, skepticism about misinformation, and increased civic engagement.

KPIs:

- Higher average Likert scale scores in post-programme surveys.
- Percentage of participants reporting positive attitude changes in interviews.

Assessment Measures:

- Surveys to measure attitudes toward media and misinformation.
- Qualitative interviews or focus groups to examine perception shifts.

4. Behaviour

Outcomes: Tangible changes in participants' media consumption habits and civic participation.

KPIs:

- Percentage increase in self-reported responsible media engagement.
- Increased frequency of participation in civic or democratic events.

Assessment Measures:

- Self-reported surveys tracking changes in media habits and online behaviours.
- Observational studies to assess engagement in civic and democratic processes.

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Find example *Outcomes, indicators* and survey questions bank [HERE](#).

Evaluating Intervention Quality: Meeting Standards for Maximum Impact

Ensuring high standards in intervention design goes beyond measuring impact.

Key Dimensions and Their Indicators for Effective Educational Interventions:

1. **Relevance:**

Criteria: Alignment with educational goals, addressing current media landscape challenges, needs of diverse audiences, and societal relevance.

2. **Impact:**

Criteria: Significant and measurable improvements in both media literacy and digital skills among participants, noticeable progress in one or both areas, consistency in participant outcomes, and evidence of long-term benefits

3. **Accessibility:**

Criteria: Availability in multiple languages, usability for diverse learning needs, device compatibility, and consideration of economic barriers.

4. **Engagement:**

Criteria: Level of participation, interaction, integration of interactive elements, and opportunities for peer collaboration and feedback.

5. **Effectiveness of pedagogy:**

Criteria: Evidence-based teaching methods, active learning strategies, scaffolding skills, differentiation, and real-world examples.

Evaluating Intervention Quality

6. **Assessment and feedback:**

Criteria: Clear objectives, variety of assessments, timely feedback, and opportunities for self-assessment and reflection.

7. **Sustainability:**

Criteria: Adequate funding, partnerships, integration into education systems, and capacity building among educators.

8. **Ethical considerations:**

Criteria: Protection of privacy, promotion of diverse perspectives, avoidance of bias, adherence to copyright, and ethical considerations.

9. **Innovation and adaptability:**

Criteria: Use of emerging technologies, responsiveness to media changes, experimentation with new methods, and scalability.

By following these standards, interventions are more likely to reach their goals and deliver meaningful results.

Generic Rubric to be used for Intervention quality evaluation can be found [here](#).

Adaptable Generic Rubric for Evaluating Intervention Quality (1/3)

Media Literacy and Digital Skills evaluation rubric

This rubric provides a structured framework for evaluating media literacy and digital skills initiatives, allowing for comprehensive assessment and targeted improvement efforts. Adjust scoring ranges and descriptors to fit specific evaluation goals and contexts.

Criteria	Exceeds Expectations (4)	Meets Expectations (3)	Needs Improvement (2)	Does Not Meet Expectations (1)
1. Relevance	Demonstrates clear alignment with current media landscape challenges, addressing diverse audience needs, and relevance to societal issues.	Generally aligns with media landscape challenges and addresses some audience needs, but lacks depth in relevance to societal issues.	Partial alignment with media landscape challenges and limited addressing of audience needs, with minimal relevance to societal issues.	Lacks alignment with media landscape challenges, fails to address audience needs, and lacks relevance to societal issues.
2. Impact	Shows significant and measurable improvements in both media literacy and digital skills among participants.	Demonstrates noticeable improvements in either media literacy or digital skills among participants.	Exhibits limited improvements or inconsistencies in media literacy and digital skills among participants.	Shows minimal to no improvements in media literacy and digital skills among participants.
3. Accessibility	Ensures resources are available in multiple languages, user-friendly for individuals with diverse learning needs, compatible with different devices and internet connections, and considers economic barriers.	Provides resources available in multiple languages, user-friendly for some individuals, compatible with some devices, and considers some economic barriers.	Offers resources with limited language options, limited user-friendliness, compatibility with select devices, and minimal consideration of economic barriers.	It provides inadequate resources, limited language options, lack of user-friendliness, compatibility issues, and no consideration of economic barriers.

Adaptable Generic Rubric for Evaluating Intervention Quality (2/3)

Criteria	Exceeds Expectations (4)	Meets Expectations (3)	Needs Improvement (2)	Does Not Meet Expectations (1)
4. Engagement	Encourages high levels of participation and interaction among learners, educators, and other stakeholders, with interactive elements and opportunities for collaboration and feedback.	Promotes moderate levels of participation and interaction among learners, educators, and other stakeholders, with some interactive elements and limited opportunities for collaboration and feedback.	Supports low levels of participation and interaction among learners, educators, and other stakeholders, with minimal interactive elements and limited opportunities for collaboration and feedback.	Fails to promote participation and interaction among learners, educators, and other stakeholders, lacks interactive elements, and provides no opportunities for collaboration and feedback.
5. Pedagogy	Utilizes evidence-based teaching methods, active learning strategies, scaffolding of skills development, differentiation of instruction, and integration of real-world examples.	Applies some evidence-based teaching methods, active learning strategies, scaffolding of skills development, differentiation of instruction, and integration of real-world examples.	Implements limited evidence-based teaching methods, active learning strategies, scaffolding of skills development, differentiation of instruction, and integration of real-world examples.	Lacks evidence-based teaching methods, active learning strategies, scaffolding of skills development, differentiation of instruction, and integration of real-world examples.
6. Assessment and Feedback	Establishes clear learning objectives and assessment criteria, utilizes various assessment methods, provides timely feedback, and offers opportunities for self-assessment and reflection.	Defines learning objectives and assessment criteria, uses some assessment methods, offers feedback, and provides some opportunities for self-assessment and reflection.	Provides limited learning objectives and assessment criteria, uses few assessment methods, offers infrequent feedback, and offers minimal opportunities for self-assessment and reflection.	Fail to establish learning objectives and assessment criteria, lacks assessment methods, provides no feedback, and offers no opportunities for self-assessment and reflection.

Adaptable Generic Rubric for Evaluating Intervention Quality (3/3)

Criteria	Exceeds Expectations (4)	Meets Expectations (3)	Needs Improvement (2)	Does Not Meet Expectations (1)
7. Sustainability	Secures adequate funding and resources, establishes partnerships, integrates initiatives into formal and informal education systems, and builds capacity among educators and trainers.	Obtains some funding and resources, establishes some partnerships, partially integrates initiatives into education systems, and partially builds capacity among educators and trainers.	Secures limited funding and resources, establishes minimal partnerships, superficially integrates initiatives into education systems, and provides limited capacity building.	Lacks adequate funding and resources, establishes no partnerships, fails to integrate initiatives into education systems, and provides no capacity building.
8. Ethical Considerations	Protects users' privacy and data rights, promotes diverse perspectives, avoids bias and misinformation, adheres to copyright principles, and considers cultural and ethical norms.	It considers users' privacy and data rights, promotes some diverse perspectives, attempts to avoid some bias and misinformation, adheres to some copyright principles, and partially considers cultural and ethical norms.	Offers limited consideration of users' privacy and data rights, promotes limited diverse perspectives, presents occasional bias and misinformation, adheres to minimal copyright principles, and superficially considers cultural and ethical norms.	Provides inadequate consideration of users' privacy and data rights, lacks promotion of diverse perspectives, demonstrates the presence of bias and misinformation, fails to adhere to copyright principles, and disregards cultural and ethical norms.
9. Innovation and Adaptability	Integrates emerging technologies, responds to changes in the media landscape, experiments with teaching approaches, and scales initiatives effectively.	Some integration of emerging technologies, some response to changes in the media landscape limited experimentation with teaching approaches, and partial scalability of initiatives.	Limited integration of emerging technologies, minimal response to changes in the media landscape, superficial experimentation with teaching approaches, and limited scalability of initiatives.	Inadequate integration of emerging technologies, no response to changes in media landscape, lack of experimentation with teaching approaches, and absence of scalability of initiatives.

Further Reading & Resources

- [Bank of outcomes, indicators, survey Questions](#)
- [Guidance Essential digital skills framework](#)
- [WHO Europe Guide: Media and Information Literacy for Public Health](#)
- [Ofcom Media Literacy Toolkit: Promoting Informed Media Use](#)
- [Media & Learning: Resources on Media Literacy](#)
- [The Digital Inclusion Evaluation Toolkit: Bank of Outcomes, Indicators and Survey Questions \(Just Economics, 2017\)](#)
- [DCMS Online Media Literacy Evidence Review \(2020\)](#)
- [LSE Rapid Evidence Assessment on Online Misinformation and Media Literacy \(2021\)](#)
- [DCMS Online Media Literacy Strategy \(2021\)](#)
- [Cross-sectoral Challenges to Media Literacy \(DSIT, 2023\)](#)

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Section 3: Making It Happen

How Do You Implement an Evaluation?

With your plan in place, it is time to bring your evaluation to life. This section focuses on executing the intervention, choosing appropriate methods, collecting data, and ensuring engagement. All elements work together to capture a holistic view of the intervention's impact.

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End Beneficiaries: Know Your Target Group

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Intervention Evaluation with the Target Group in Mind

Why it matters: Planning evaluations with the audience in mind ensures **engagement, inclusivity, and reliable results.**

Key Considerations for Audience-Centered Evaluations:

A. Target Group Characteristics:

Identifying and addressing prerequisite needs and knowledge gaps makes evaluations more accessible and engaging for the target audience, resulting in more accurate findings. *For example*, older adults may need more focus on foundational digital skills due to challenges with technology access and experience.

Accommodating audience preferences, like preferred formats and communication methods, makes evaluations more engaging, and encourages higher participation. *For example*, using video tutorials for younger audiences captures their attention better than text-based materials.

Accommodating the special needs of diverse populations enhances inclusivity by removing barriers to participation. *For example*, providing text-to-speech options or simplified navigation for visually impaired

participants allows them to interact with the evaluation content fully and independently, ensuring their feedback is represented.

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A European Commission study (2001) found that tailored digital literacy programmes for the elderly increased engagement by 40%, compared to generic courses.

A UNESCO study (2020) found that culturally tailored digital literacy programmes had a 35% higher completion rate than generic ones.

Intervention Evaluation with the Target Group in Mind

B. Content Relevance:

Tailoring evaluation content to resonate with the audience's real-life experiences increases its **relevance** and **engagement**, making participants more likely to be invested in the evaluation process. For example, focusing on **children's** online safety makes evaluations more meaningful for parents.

Employing culturally sensitive content during evaluation fosters a sense of **relevance**, enhancing participant engagement and adequate responses. For example, using media examples from participants' home countries in a literacy programme helps immigrant communities feel respected and engaged.

Intervention Evaluation with the Target Group in Mind

C. Engagement Factors:

Understanding and addressing motivations and concerns of the target fosters **engagement**. This increases the evaluation's accuracy by encouraging honest and open feedback and willingness to participate. For example, in a digital literacy programme for job seekers, explaining how their feedback will help tailor job-relevant skills can motivate them to provide honest input, as they see a direct benefit to their career goals.

Tip: For longer evaluations, gather feedback at regular intervals—through quick surveys or brief check-ins—to stay aligned with participant needs and make timely adjustments for more effective evaluation.

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Target Groups: What To Consider – Practical Examples (1/2)

Consideration	Description	Example
Demographic	Tailor evaluation metrics to capture differences in age, gender, ethnicity, socio-economic status, and education, reflecting how these factors impact engagement and outcomes.	Use demographic-specific feedback surveys to assess relevance and impact for different target groups.
Digital Proficiency	Adapt evaluation tools to match participants' digital skill levels, ensuring the assessment is accessible and understandable for all.	Implement simplified surveys or digital literacy quizzes for seniors with limited experience.
Language Diversity	Conduct evaluations in multiple languages to ensure all participants can fully express their experience and feedback.	Use bilingual evaluators or translation tools for communities with high non-native speakers.
Accessibility Needs	Develop inclusive evaluation formats (e.g., screen readers, braille, large print) to gather feedback from participants with disabilities.	Provide evaluation materials in braille or audio formats for visually impaired participants.
Cultural Sensitivity	Frame evaluation questions to respect participants' cultural perspectives, ensuring unbiased enquiry.	Use culturally relevant imagery or scenarios in evaluation activities for diverse communities.
Geographic Location	Consider variations in connectivity and tech access when conducting remote evaluations, adjusting for rural or low-internet-access areas.	Distribute paper surveys or conduct phone interviews for participants in remote regions.

Target Groups: What To Consider – Practical Examples (2/2)

Consideration	Description	Example
Prior Experience	Assess how participants' prior exposure to media literacy impacts their programme engagement and outcomes.	Segment results based on familiarity with media, using pre-surveys on past media exposure.
Learning Preferences	Account for different format preferences in evaluation methods to capture diverse ways of engagement and comprehension.	Use visual or auditory formats in evaluations to cater to varied learning preferences.
Psychological Factors	Design evaluations with sensitivity to mental health factors, ensuring questions are non-stressful and focus on well-being.	Exclude triggering topics and use supportive language in feedback forms for vulnerable groups.
Access to Resources	Evaluate the availability and impact of resources like digital devices and internet connectivity on learning outcomes.	Include questions about device access and tech comfort levels in assessments for underserved groups.
Community Engagement	Involve local stakeholders in the evaluation process to gather more nuanced feedback.	Partner with community leaders to facilitate group interviews and community-led feedback sessions.

Examples of Matching Evaluation Goals & Methods for Various Target Groups (1/2)

Target Group	Example Evaluation Goal	Example Evaluation Method
Teens	Critical Thinking on Misinformation	Scenario-Based Quizzes: Create online quizzes with realistic scenarios (e.g., identifying fake news on social media). Quizzes can assess critical thinking and fact-checking behavior pre- and post-intervention.
	Social Media Awareness	Peer-led Focus Groups: Use focus groups facilitated by peers to discuss social media habits and personal experiences with misinformation. This approach encourages open sharing in an age-relevant setting.
Young Children	Safe Online Navigation	Story-based Interactive Surveys: Use storyboards that follow relatable characters navigating online activities (e.g., watching videos, using apps). Ask simple questions about safety decisions at each story step.
	Basic Digital Literacy	Parental Observation Feedback: Have parents/guardians complete pre- and post-intervention surveys on observed changes in children's tech behaviors (e.g., understanding safe app usage).
NEET Individuals	Job-Related Digital Skills	Skills-Based Assessments: Use short, practical tasks (e.g., creating a professional email or completing an online job application) to measure practical skills relevant to employability.
	Motivation and Confidence	Personal Journals: Ask participants to keep journals noting their comfort and confidence using digital tools over time, which can be analyzed qualitatively to assess motivational changes.
Teachers	Classroom Integration of Media Literacy	Lesson Plan Reflections: Have teachers submit short reflections on how they incorporated media literacy topics into their lessons, including what worked well and challenges faced.
	Impact on Student Engagement	Student Surveys: Administer pre- and post-intervention surveys to students on engagement and understanding of media literacy concepts, helping to indirectly measure teacher effectiveness.

Examples of Matching Evaluation Goals & Methods for Various Target Groups (1/2)

Target Group	Example Evaluation Goal	Example Evaluation Method
People with Disabilities	Accessibility and Usability	One-on-One Interviews: Conduct interviews asking about ease of use, comfort, and any challenges encountered in accessing the digital tools, especially for assistive tech users.
	Digital Confidence and Skill Retention	Accessible Digital Skills Quiz: Design a short digital skills quiz accessible to those using assistive devices (e.g., screen readers) to measure retention and identify gaps.
Socio-economically Disadvantaged Groups	Foundational Digital Literacy	Baseline and Follow-Up Assessments: Start with a baseline assessment of digital skills (e.g., using basic software, understanding safe browsing) and repeat it post-intervention to measure improvement.
	Resource Accessibility	Low-Tech Feedback Tools: Provide simple feedback options, like phone interviews or SMS-based surveys, to assess the accessibility and relevance of digital resources used in the intervention.
Seniors	Basic Digital Literacy Confidence	Confidence Self-Rating Scales: Use simple, visual scales (e.g., rate your confidence with email from 1-5) before and after intervention sessions to assess growth in digital confidence.
	Usability of Tools and Methods	Post-Session Checklists: Use short checklists after each session, asking about ease of use for each tool and gathering direct feedback on comfort and usability.

Tailored evaluation goals and methods provide meaningful insights for each unique audience.

Annex: Evaluator's Checklist for Target Group Considerations

Tick Box	Category	Considerations
<input type="checkbox"/>	Demographic	Have I tailored metrics to capture age, gender, ethnicity, socio-economic status, and education? Have I used feedback tools specific to demographics to assess relevance and impact?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Digital Proficiency	Have I adapted tools to participants' digital skill levels for accessibility? Have I simplified surveys or provided digital literacy quizzes for beginners?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Language Diversity	Have I ensured evaluation availability in multiple languages? Have I arranged for bilingual evaluators or translation tools for non-native speakers?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Accessibility Needs	Have I developed inclusive formats (e.g., braille, large print) for participants with disabilities? Have I provided materials in accessible formats (e.g., braille or audio)?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Cultural Sensitivity	Have I framed questions to respect cultural perspectives and avoid bias? Have I used culturally relevant imagery or scenarios?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Geographic Location	Have I considered connectivity and tech access for remote evaluations? Have I provided alternatives (e.g., paper surveys or phone interviews) for low-access areas?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Prior Experience	Have I assessed participants' prior exposure to inform engagement and outcomes? Have I segmented results based on familiarity with the subject?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Preferences	Have I accounted for different format preferences? Have I included visual or auditory formats for varied preferences?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Psychological Factors	Have I designed questions considering mental health sensitivity? Have I used supportive and non-triggering language?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Access to Resources	Have I evaluated participants' access to devices and connectivity? Have I included questions on comfort with tech use and internet access?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Community Engagement	Have I involved local stakeholders to gather nuanced feedback? Have I partnered with community leaders for group interviews?

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Sampling for Evaluation

What is it: Inviting people to participate in the evaluation in the right way so that they represent those who (could) participate in and benefit from your intervention.

Why sampling matters:

Good sampling means that you don't have to ask everyone to participate (saving costs) and that the results of your evaluation are not severely biased (i.e. they do not under or over-represent certain groups).

You will make better decisions because you will be able to trust the results of the evaluation!

Sampling: What to Keep in Mind

In large interventions (e.g., school children, families, the long-term unemployed), full participation isn't always feasible—making sampling essential.

There are **two important things to keep in mind** in relation to sampling:

Your **population** includes those in the intervention group (participants) and the control group (potential beneficiaries who haven't participated yet)

Bias occurs when the selection method skews inclusion chances for certain groups within the target population. Bias hinders **accurate representation** in evaluations, making it harder to trust that results truly reflect the intervention's impact on all participants.

Sampling Types

In this toolkit we discuss the following types of sampling:

- People get selected by chance from a contact list you have of all (potential) participants (**Random Sampling**)
- Group (potential) participants by certain characteristics and select within these groups (**Stratified / Quota Sampling**)
- Select individuals from within pre-existing groups or areas (**Cluster Sampling**)
- Start with a few individuals that you know or can reach, and ask them bring others (**Snowball Sampling**)
- Let anyone who wants to participate participate, often through self-selection (**Volunteer/ Convenience Sampling**)

Volunteer

Snowball

Cluster

Quota

Random

Random sampling carries the lowest **risk of bias**, while volunteer sampling has the highest risk.

Random Sampling

In random sampling, every single individual in the population has an equal chance of being selected.

You repeat invitations to specific individuals selected so that it is not only the first ones to respond that participate in the evaluation.

This ensures generalisability of findings to all current and potential future participants in the intervention and minimal bias.

A full contact list (emails, addresses, telephone numbers) of the population is needed to recruit individuals randomly.

It is very **unlikely** that you will be able to do proper random sampling but you might be able to do random sampling amongst all those who have signed up for the intervention.

Stratified/Quota Sampling

In stratified sampling, the population of potential participants is divided into distinct groups or strata (e.g. based on gender, age, income, or education) to ensure that each group is represented in the sample.

This is particularly important when you are interested in how different groups compare and you want to make sure that smaller groups are represented in sufficient numbers.

You need to have a contact list for each group you want to represent.

Participants are then randomly selected within their groups.

Cluster Sampling

If you do not have access to a contact list for all (potential) participants to randomly sample them, dividing the population into smaller groups or locations (clusters) for which you do have this information could be more convenient.

For example, you might have information on the characteristics of (people who frequent) specific schools, libraries, sports clubs, or community centres. You select these locations, interventions, club members and ask all the individuals in this 'cluster' to participate.

Used when it is easier, cheaper or more ethical to include whole groups instead of individuals.

All members of the clusters must be invited.

Since you have information on the people in a cluster, you can understand who has not responded to your invitation or which part of your population remains underrepresented because you did not select a cluster.

Snowball Sampling

This sampling is particularly useful when target groups aren't easy to reach and when you do not have contact information of the population or the locations / clusters where you might find them.

You select a diverse group of initial participants based on the knowledge you have of them and ask them to involve other (potential) participants in the evaluation.

Defining recruitment criteria (e.g., age, gender, education, ethnicity) helps reduce bias in the intervention evaluation sample.

If the initial group of individuals is not diverse the rest of the sample will also be biased, since people know people who are like them and they like.

Volunteer/Convenience Sampling

A volunteer sample consists of those who you have easy access to and those who step forward themselves to participate.

A key advantage is securing enough participants, but there is a high risk of bias—volunteers often include those with time or strong opinions on the intervention.

To reduce bias, the call for participation should be as wide and as accessible as possible.

Send multiple invitations, post notices in various locations, follow up via email, and ensure the evaluation is in an accessible language.

Examples of Different Sampling Formats

Random:

You are evaluating perceptions of the national ML&DS curriculum rollout.

You have a **database of tens of thousands** of students and teachers in the country, but you can't contact everyone because it is too costly.*

Therefore, 2500 students and 1000 teachers are **randomly selected** from all schools to evaluate the new curriculum. Students and teachers are listed randomly (i.e. not by last name or region or age), and every 100th student and every 50th teacher is contacted.

Follow up with initial invitees by sending at least **three reminders** at different times and days if they have not responded. If there is no response, replace them with the next person on your list.

Once you reach 2500 students and 1000 teachers you stop collecting data (allowing those who started to finish and include them in the questionnaire).

Examples of Different Sampling Formats

Quota:

To measure the impact of a ML&DS intervention rolled out in the region amongst teenagers of disadvantaged and more privileged backgrounds, you select a city and a small town in the region where the intervention has taken place.

There you design a sample using the city and town registries that ensures **equal representation** of age, gender and socio-economic background (SES) groups and equal numbers of those who have participated (P) in the intervention and those who have not (NP) following the logic in this table*:

		Year 9 (13-14 yrs old)		Year 10 (14-15 yrs old)		Year 11 (15-16 years old)	
		P	NP	P	NP	P	NP
High SES	Boys	50	50	50	50	50	50
	Girls	50	50	50	50	50	50
Low SES	Boys	50	50	50	50	50	50
	Girls	50	50	50	50	50	50

*50 is a target quota often used by researchers because it allows you to do meaningful statistical comparisons between groups. The quota you set is a minimum and should be realistic and relevant to the types of analysis you want to do.

Examples of Different Sampling Formats

Cluster:

Your organisation conducts nationwide seminars for families on ML&DS in **community centres** on disinformation and needs to assess participants' media literacy and learning.

Since **surveying all families is costly** and **training** all those delivering the seminar in evaluation **is not feasible**, in each region two cities and two villages are selected in which interventions took place. Then in these cities and villages, two neighbourhoods are selected, and within these, two centres in which seminars took place are selected.

Seminar leaders in these centres **are trained** to administer the questionnaire, ensuring **all families in the centre are invited** to participate.

Data on the characteristics of **those who did not participate in the evaluation** (assuming that the centre has this information) is also collected to check that the sample represents all participants.

Examples of Different Sampling Formats

Snowball:

You are evaluating the impact of a programme focussed on helping migrants and asylum seekers gain digital skills for employment.

Since there are often issues of trust and literacy in these populations, they can be considered **hard to reach**. Therefore, you ask a select group of volunteers leading the intervention to **invite 5 to 10 people with different profiles** and backgrounds to participate and then ask those who participated to suggest or ask others to participate.

The intervention leaders should come from different **programmes** and **backgrounds** (e.g. gender, ethnicity, age) themselves and should be explicitly instructed to ask individuals from different backgrounds

For example, you ask the leader of an intervention at a big centre in the capital city and the representative of a small charity delivering the intervention in a rural area of the country.

Examples of Different Sampling Formats

Volunteer:

After completing an ML&DS course (online), all participants are asked to fill out a feedback form about the topics covered during the sessions.

There are no resources to offer payment for participation in the evaluation and their participation is completely voluntary. You **invite everyone** (e.g. via a link in the course material, by handing them a feedback form, or by sending an email to follow up). You **just take those who completed** the questionnaire without **following up** with those who did not respond.

This is the most likely scenario for interventions with **vulnerable populations** or who do **courses online** with no contact or background information available for participants.

Your sample is very **unlikely to be representative**, for example, they might be people in the extremes: those who were very satisfied or very disappointed with the course. You need to take this into consideration when analysing results.

Toolkit Structure

1. Introduction

2. Laying the
Groundwork

3. Making it Happen

3.1. End
Beneficiaries &
Target Groups

3.2. Selecting the
Sample

3.3. Evaluation
Research Design

3.4. Intervention
Evaluation
Measurement

4. Unpacking the
Insights

4.1. Data Analysis

4.2. Ethical & Data
Protection
Guidance

5. Telling the Story

5.1. Reporting &
Dissemination

6. Continuous
Improvement &
Sustainability

7. Intervention
Evaluation
Recommendations

8. Useful Resources

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Evaluation/Research Design

Why it matters: A well-designed evaluation ensures reliable results, helping to refine and improve the intervention for future rounds or different contexts.

Terminology

Pre-test : measuring the characteristics, and ICT access, skill, use and outcomes of use of participants at the start of the intervention.

Post-test : measuring these at the end (immediate post-test) and/or some time after the intervention (delayed post-test).

Treatment group: those who are participating in the intervention.

Control group: those who could benefit from the intervention but are not yet participating in your intervention (perhaps in another one).

Experimental Design

Experimental design (ED) is considered the **Gold standard for evaluation**. In its purest form ED is known as Randomised Controlled Trials (RCTs).

RCTs consist of a pre-test, a post-test and a delayed post-test. People from your sample are randomly assigned to a treatment group or to a **control group**. Afterwards, comparisons between groups are made in terms of the difference in their pre- and post-test results.

ED can be applied in the places where your intervention takes place as long as everyone in the sample has an equal chance of being in the treatment and control group.

It is very unlikely that you will be able to do an evaluation integrating all aspects of RCT experimental design in ML&DS interventions.

A = difference between the results in the pre-test and post-test in the treatment group

B = difference between the results in the pre-test and post-test in the control group

(Ideally you would be able to compare answers from the same individuals - assign each person an ID)

Quasi-Experimental Design

When participants are already enrolled in existing interventions, and there is no access to non-participants or alternative interventions, a **quasi-experimental design** (QED) is commonly used. QED typically includes a pre-test, post-test, and sometimes a delayed post-test. Unlike RCTs, participants are not randomly assigned to treatment or control groups—only a treatment group exists. The evaluation is conducted with those participating in the intervention.

Since there is no control group, it is more difficult to determine whether the changes measured are solely due to the intervention or influenced by external factors, such as the kinds of people who signed up to the intervention.

Non-Experimental Design

Non-experimental design is the simplest and most flexible approach, relying mostly on participants' **self-reports**. It provides evidence of **correlation**, not causation. Participants reflect on what they learned and the intervention's actual or expected impact after completing it.

Since pre-intervention conditions were not measured, post-intervention findings cannot be solely attributed to the intervention. Participants who complete the course and answer the evaluation questionnaire may have already been more skilled or intensive users.

Measurement is conducted through a one-time post-test, often using surveys to assess key aspects of the intervention (e.g., media literacy & digital skills, technology use, learnings, and satisfaction). Socio-demographic data are collected and correlated to analyse who benefited and how.

Pros and Cons of Different Ways of Evaluating

Experimental Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- As participants are randomly selected, all have the same chance to be invited.- Uses a control group to compare and estimate the impact of the intervention.- It is very hard and expensive to implement in practice.
Quasi-Experimental Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- It assesses conditions before the intervention to accurately track changes over time.- Participant selection based on people volunteering or signing up themselves.- Lower costs than Experimental Design.- Harder to control bias in participants selection.- Since there is no control group, comparisons with people receiving no/alternative intervention are not possible.
Non-Experimental Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Least expensive evaluation method- People feel like their opinion matters when asked to participate in evaluation- Without pre-intervention data, assessing the intervention's effects is more challenging.

Examples of Different Design Cases

Experimental Design	<p>The Ministry of Education is piloting a new ML&DS course in particular schools in the country. Pre- and post-tests are conducted with students in a school where the course is implemented. In a school with similar characteristics where the course has not yet been implemented, you ask students to fill in the same questionnaire at the same time.</p> <p>The pre- and post-questionnaires have questions on student: characteristics (e.g. socio-demographics, academic achievements, wellbeing), media literacy and digital skills, and use of digital and other media. Differences in responses between the pre and post tests are compared for the schools with the course and without the course implemented.</p>
Quasi-Experimental Design	<p>You are evaluating the impact of a one-month media and digital skills course for employees from a charity working with migrants.</p> <p>Participants take pre- and post-tests, and the results are compared to measure the impact of the course on their ability to use digital media for professional and personal development, and their understanding of why digital skills are important for migrants.</p>
Non-Experimental Design	<p>A charity offering drop-in sessions for unemployed people on online job applications wants to assess attendees' skill development and satisfaction with the support provided and ask them to fill out a questionnaire after the support session.</p>

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8. Useful Resources

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Evaluation Methods: Measurement

Why it matters: How you measure the characteristics of your participants and the impact of your intervention determines what types of analysis you can do and what types of conclusions you can draw.

Terminology

Quantitative : measuring the characteristics, and ICT access, skills, uses, and outcomes of use of participants through surveys, performance tests or usage analytics gathering data that can be analysed with statistics (e.g., correlating pre- and post-test results).

Qualitative : measuring participants' experiences and learnings through interviews or observations, gathering data that can be analysed through text or audio-visual analysis methods (e.g. ,vignette, thematic or discourse analysis).

Mixed methods: using a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods.

Quantitative Evaluation

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Pre-Post Surveys

Typical measurement method based on repetition using the same diagnostic tools

Used **before** the intervention (training, coaching, implementation of a pedagogical/andragogy innovation) and **afterwards**.

Tools can be **self-constructed** (depending on the type of target group) or **imported from ready-made measurement solutions**.

Enables the evaluation of the effectiveness of the applied learning activities immediately after the training as well as the evaluation of the **effectiveness in the long term** (post-test repetition).

Evaluation of the effectiveness of training-interventions usually uses **numerical scales** and **effect size coefficients** (e.g., Cohen's d, Hedges' g, Eta-squared η^2).

Such measurement makes it possible to map changes in **knowledge, skills, attitudes** or **behaviour**.

Pre-Post Surveys: Examples

A group of senior citizens is taking part in a “Safe Internet” workshop. A pre-test assesses their knowledge of phishing, password management and recognising fake e-mails. After the workshop, the participants take the same quiz, and the results are compared to assess knowledge growth.

A group of long-term unemployed people participates in a training course on using LinkedIn for job search. A pre-training survey asks them about their attitudes toward social media platforms in the context of their careers (e.g., “LinkedIn is a tool to help me find a job”). After the workshop, their attitudes are measured again.

Standardised Assessments

Based in most cases on a clearly defined **theoretical framework** (e.g., international ECDL/ICDL, DIGCOMP).

May be developed on the basis of locally implemented projects (e.g., Croatian concept of **digital maturity measurement** - project awarded by the European Commission within the RegioStar competition).

Often used in **formal education** (e.g., matriculation exam in computer science) or **non-formal education** (obtaining a recognised ICDL/ECDL-type certificate).

In many educational systems in this type of certification, it is possible to specify the **level of ML&DS proficiency** (from basic to advanced).

Based on **self-declaration** or knowledge and skills **testing** requiring access to a computer lab and supervision by an examiner.

Standardized Assessments: Examples

Using the DIGCOMP framework to assess digital competencies in various areas (e.g., information processing, communication, content creation).

Practical application:

- Long-term unemployed or NEET youth (not participating in education, employment or training): Course centres introduce a mock exam that tests the ability to work with a spreadsheet, word processor and e-learning platform, according to DIGCOMP requirements.
- An ICT course for seniors uses a self-administered test for using a smartphone and apps such as Zoom or Google Meet. Performance is assessed according to the DIGCOMP framework, with levels ranging from basic (A1) to advanced (C2).

Usage Analytics

This approach allows the **automatic measurement** of interactions on knowledge and skills testing platforms, determining the level of engagement (e.g., time spent solving tasks, number of attempts at solving tasks)

Systems based on usage analytics provide an opportunity to capture learning objectives, learning content, forms and methods on e-learning platforms that cause the **most difficulties for learners.**

Allows **monitoring** and **optimisation** of learning materials that are less effective.

Is implemented with strict attention to the specifics of the group concerned and is tailored to the learning content.

Allows for the **prediction** of **failure** or **drop-out** from the training programme reinforcing ML&DS.

Usage Analytics: Practical Implementation

Measuring the level of engagement in an e-learning course

Context: A group of long-term unemployed people takes an online course on how to use digital tools (e.g., Google Docs, Canva).

Example: If the system detects that most participants repeat a word processing task three or more times, the instructor adds an additional video module explaining the basic functions of the editor.

Analysing training content effectiveness

Context: Seniors take a course on how to use the Internet safely (e.g., recognising phishing, creating strong passwords).

Example: Seeing that 70% of responses to a phishing email task are incorrect, the instructor revises the content, adding more examples and explaining common phishing schemes.

Qualitative Evaluation

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Focus Groups

Focus groups provide valuable insights into **learners' opinions** on different aspects of the ML&DS training process. They enable reflection on the programme by identifying areas for improvement, such as adjusting content or increasing training hours. Additionally, they help capture group dynamics related to ML&DS learning, offering a collective perspective that differs from individual viewpoints.

A focus group is a **structured discussion** where participants with shared characteristics (e.g., challenges in using digital tools) discuss specific topics, such as digital and media competencies. Led by a moderator following a predefined guide, participants share experiences, opinions, and insights, helping to understand how people use technology and what their needs are.

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Interviews

Interviews are a **basic, low-cost** method for collecting data on ML&DS development. They can be conducted using a structured script or through informal conversations between trainers and learners. This approach enables continuous evaluation of both short- and long-term learning goals.

Unlike standard knowledge and skills tests, interviews offer **deeper insights** into learning strengths and weaknesses. They help structure the learning experience by identifying typologies of strengths and challenges. Well-crafted questions also encourage **reflection** on the ML&DS learning process.

This method is particularly useful in digital inclusion efforts for individuals with very low ML&DS levels, ensuring they receive the necessary support from trainers.

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Examples of an Interview Scenario

Background knowledge and use of technology

- Do you own a digital device such as a smartphone, tablet or computer?
- How often do you use the Internet?
- Do you feel confident using these devices?

Perceived difficulties

- What do you find most difficult when using new technologies?
- Have you ever needed help using a device? What kind of help?

Reflection on the learning process

- What do you find easiest when learning new technologies?
- Is there anything that particularly helped you learn (e.g., videos, h

Suggestions for the training

- Is there anything we could change in the training to make it more l
- Does the pace and delivery of the training meet your needs?

Attitudes and emotions towards new technologies

- Do you think that using new technologies can improve your qualit
- Are you afraid of anything related to technologies (e.g., online sca

Content Analysis

During the assessment of the level of digital competence, work results can be used (e.g., completion of a task in the software indicated by the trainer).

Content analysis requires the involvement of not only the learner, but also the ML&DS **trainer** who, according to clearly defined criteria, evaluates the results of the work, which are different kinds of digital artefacts developed or edited by learners.

An example of content analysis in the development of teachers' digital competence can be the evaluation of the quality of prepared open educational resources (Tomczyk et al., 2024; Guillén-Gámez et al., 2024; Tomczyk et al., 2023).

Other examples include making a website, setting up a profile in a specialized service (e.g., a service for job seekers).

Observation

Observation is a fundamental method for evaluating any teaching process.

It can be **directed** (e.g., assessing whether an ICT task follows a specific pattern) or **free** (e.g., evaluating trainee activities in problem-based learning).

This method enables progress assessment at **both individual and group levels**, providing insights for ongoing evaluation of learner engagement.

Observations also allow trainers to **continuously adjust content**, methods, and teaching approaches, ensuring the learning process aligns with the needs of the pedagogical or andragogical intervention.

Observation in Practice

Analysis of progress in learning to use basic digital tools: observation of how participants handle tasks such as sending emails, using word processing or browsing the Internet. Evaluation can include both the correctness of the tasks and the time taken to complete them.

Assessing engagement in problem-based projects (PBL): analyse participant activity in projects that require solving real-world problems using digital tools (e.g., resume preparation by unemployed people).

Analysis of social media use: observation of how participants use platforms such as Facebook or Twitter to communicate and acquire information that the course instructor posts. Assessment can include both the ability to use these tools and the quality and desirability of the content posted.

Case Studies

Many ML&DS interventions have a documented and accessible training programme. Such materials serve as secondary sources for analysis, facilitating the transfer or refinement of similar interventions.

Analysis of individual or group experiences makes it possible to transpose them to other interventions, using not only the training programme and evaluation tools.

Evaluation results from other interventions (e.g., in the form of reports, scientific articles, open databases) can serve as a **reference point** for **measuring their own**, thus **enabling comparative effectiveness**.

Case Studies: Examples

Analysis of training programme documentation	Review available digital and media literacy training programmes that have been implemented with other disadvantaged groups. This analysis can help transfer or refine similar interventions to new groups.
Use of evaluation results from other interventions	Leveraging evaluation results from other interventions—such as reports, scientific articles, and open databases—provides a benchmark for measuring the effectiveness of your own programmes. Comparing these results helps assess and refine your intervention’s impact.
Analysis of good practice examples	Analysing best practices in digital and media literacy training programmes helps identify effective methods, avoid mistakes, inspire innovation, and set quality standards. It also helps to better tailor programmes to the needs of target groups, strengthens cooperation between organisations, and makes it possible to evaluate the effectiveness of different approaches.

Mixed-Methods Evaluation

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Triangulation

Combining the quantitative and qualitative methods mentioned in the previous slides allows to understand in a more complex way not only the level of change in ML&DS under a given intervention, but also to characterise the context that creates the conditions for this process.

Combining quantitative measurement is **more time-consuming** than using a single approach; however, it allows to capture processes both in a way that allows for comparison and to capture the causes of failures at the same time.

Triangulation is **sometimes criticised among social research methodologists** for combining **objectivity** (quantitative methods) with **subjectivity** (qualitative methods), however, paradoxically at the same time it brings many new possibilities by removing the limitations of one-dimensional ML&DS measurement.

Sequential Explanatory Design

Consists of first carrying out a **quantitative measurement** (e.g., knowledge and skills tests according to the ICDL standard) and then clarifying the reasons for failure of individual learners using **qualitative research** (e.g. in-depth or structured interviews)

An approach based on Sequential Explanatory Design makes it possible to create evaluations for the whole intervention-training programme **not only by showing descriptive statistics of the change** in ML&DS (mean, standard deviations, number of people exceeding certain intervention performance thresholds, effect size), but to **show the background** giving the opportunity for a deeper interpretation of the mathematical results

Embedded Design

This is an activity **naturally anchored in the training programme**. Evaluation is not seen as the end of a cycle of activities, but occurs with each learning objective.

ML&DS **evaluation is continuous**, allowing the intervention programme to be continually adapted to the needs and capabilities of the participants.

Elements of the training are **naturally implicit in the exercises** and do not have a clearly demarcated module (e.g., a knowledge and skills test with a limit of points for a positive evaluation of the learning outcome).

Embedded Design helps to **reduce the stress level of trainees**, which co-exists with the classical evaluation in the form of ICT knowledge and skills tests.

Embedded Design allows trainees to create a portfolio showcasing their progress in ML&DS. For example, in teacher training, this portfolio may take the form of a Padlet with a collection of self-directed tasks.

(Dis)advantages of Research Methods: Summary (1/4)

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Pre-Post Surveys	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Allow assessment of changes in knowledge, skills and attitudes before and after the intervention.● Allow assessment of the effectiveness of educational activities in the short and long term.● May be tailored to the specifics of the target group (e.g., seniors, unemployed).	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Results may be subjective for self-created tools.● May not reflect actual practical skills.● Do not always take into account contextual factors that affect outcomes.
Standardised Assessments	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Based on a well-established theoretical framework (e.g., DIGCOMP).● Allow certification of competency levels (e.g., A1 to C2).● Used in formal and informal education, which increases their versatility.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Require access to a computer lab and examiner supervision.● Costly to develop and implement at the local level.● May be limited to testing specific skills, leaving out other aspects.
Usage Analytics	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Automatically measures participant engagement on e-learning platforms.● Allows identification of difficulties and optimization of learning materials.● Allows predicting the risk of abandonment of the training programme.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Requires a sophisticated analytical system and specialized knowledge for interpretation.● Can be limited to the online environment, ignoring the offline context.● Does not take into account the subjective experience of participants.

(Dis)advantages of Research Methods: Summary (2/4)

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Focus Groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Allow in-depth analysis of participants' opinions and needs.● Allow identification of programme elements that need modification.● Provide diverse perspectives on an issue.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Results may be distorted by the dominance of some participants in the group.● Require an experienced facilitator to ensure effective discussion.● Difficult to organise in groups with diverse needs.
Interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Low-cost and easy to implement.● Allow for an understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of the learning process.● Enable in-depth reflection on the process of digital competence formation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Can be time-consuming for large numbers of participants.● Results are subjective and can be difficult to generalise.
Content Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Allows evaluation of the quality of digital artifacts (e.g., web pages) produced by participants.● Provides an opportunity to analyse the results of work in the context of clearly defined criteria.● Allows evaluation of progress based on specific results.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Requires trainer's involvement and time to carefully evaluate each result.● Can be subjective if evaluation criteria are not explicit.● Does not allow full evaluation of the thought processes behind the tasks performed.

(Dis)advantages of Research Methods: Summary (3/4)

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Observations	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Make it possible to assess progress at both the individual and group levels.● Help in the ongoing modification of teaching methods and content.● Provide real-time data on participant engagement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Require the presence and activity of an observer, which can affect the naturalness of behaviour.● Can be difficult to conduct in large groups.● Subjectivity of the observer can affect interpretation of results.
Case Studies	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Enable in-depth analysis of individual or group experiences.● Allow identification of good practices that can be adapted in other interventions.● Provide rich material for comparing the effectiveness of different methods.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Results may not be easily transferable to other groups or contexts.● Require time to analyse documentation and results from other programmes.● Focus on individuals may overlook broader trends.
Triangulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Combines the advantages of quantitative and qualitative methods, which allows a comprehensive evaluation of the results.● Allows identification of causes of successes and failures in interventions.● Minimises the limitations of using a single research method.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● The process of data analysis is time-consuming and requires high research competence.● Criticised for combining objective and subjective research approaches.

(Dis)advantages of Research Methods: Summary (4/4)

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Sequential Explanatory Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Allows in-depth data through a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods.• Allows identification of background and causes of quantitative results.• Provides opportunity for more accurate interpretation of statistical results.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Requires two survey phases, which increases project time.• Can be difficult to apply to groups with limited time availability.• Requires extensive resources (time and manpower) for implementation and analysis.
Embedded Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Assesses progress in a continuous manner and is naturally embedded in the training process.• Reduces participant stress levels associated with classic assessment methods.• Allows participants to build a portfolio documenting their development.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Can be less precise than classic knowledge and skills tests.• Requires precise planning to effectively integrate assessment into the training programme.• Can be difficult to implement in programmes of short duration.

Data Collection Tools: Examples

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REMEDIS Tool

	Not at all true of me (1)	Not very true of me (2)	Neither true nor untrue of me (3)	Mostly true of me (4)	Very true of me (5)	I do not understand what you mean by this (0)	I do not want to answer (99)
I know how to protect a device (e.g., with a PIN, a screen pattern, a fingerprint, facial recognition) (1)							
I know how to store photos, documents or other files on the cloud (e.g., Google Drive, iCloud) (2)							
I know how to use private browsing (e.g., incognito mode) (3)							

The REMEDIS team used pre- and post-intervention questionnaires to evaluate the effectiveness of 12 interventions to develop digital and media skills.

The tool was designed to be flexible, allowing for adaptation to specific audiences and intervention formats. The questionnaires consisted of several sections, such as socio-demographics, access to technology, digital skills, and modes and outcomes of internet use.

REMEDIS

Source: <https://zenodo.org/records/14603817>

REMEDIS Tool

	Not at all true of me (1)	Not very true of me (2)	Neither true nor untrue of me (3)	Mostly true of me (4)	Very true of me (5)	I do not understand what you mean by this (0)	I do not want to answer (99)
I know how to use advanced search functions in search engines (1)							
I know how to check if the information I find online is true (2)							
I know how to figure out if a website can be trusted (3)							

Advantages:

- Customisable questionnaires for different groups and intervention goals.
- Covers aspects ranging from technical competence to social and emotional outcomes.
- Pre- and post-intervention measurement allows assessment of progress.
- Questionnaires translated into different languages and culturally adapted.

For whom:

- Intervention participants: people from disadvantaged groups, such as NEET youth, the elderly, migrants, and people with low levels of education.
- Intervention implementers who want to measure the effectiveness of their activities.

REMEDIS

Source: <https://zenodo.org/records/14603817>

ECDL / ICDL- E-Citizen

ECDL (European Computer Driving Licence) is an international standard for the certification of digital skills, recognised in more than 100 countries. This certificate confirms practical competence in computer use, office software and Internet use, making it an important tool for supporting the development of a digital society.

Particularly noteworthy is the **E-Citizen ECDL** module, designed for beginners in the use of information and communication technologies. The programme serves to delineate the basics of computer literacy, Internet use and the use of e-services, such as email, online shopping and e-government. It aims to combat digital exclusion, especially among the elderly, migrants and those with limited access to technology.

For whom:

- Participants in basic computer and Internet training, including the elderly, migrants or those at risk of digital exclusion.
- Trainers and educational institutions that want to measure the progress of their trainees.
- Organisations that offer exams in digital competence.

Advantages:

- The tests cover various aspects of digital skills, from basic computer use to using e-services.
- Results are comparable by using international ECDL standards.
- The tool is user-friendly for people with no prior digital experience.
- It allows assessment in different languages and cultural contexts.
- Results indicate specific areas for further development, which helps design more effective interventions.

SELFIE

The **SELFIE** tool is an innovative solution created by the European Commission to help schools assess the level of digital technology use in the teaching and learning process. It is a kind of self-assessment that allows both students and teachers to express their opinions on how technology is used in school.

For whom:

- For trainers of the digitally excluded.
- For elementary, secondary and vocational schools, especially those working with students from disadvantaged groups, such as children from rural areas, students with disabilities, migrants or the socioeconomically disadvantaged.

Advantages:

- SELFIE helps identify barriers to digital education and propose tailored solutions for struggling students.
- Schools and LLL institutions can adapt the questions to the context of working with disadvantaged students, taking into account their needs.

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<https://education.ec.europa.eu/selfie>

Challenges of Research Tool Design (1/2)

Variety of Definitions

There are many definitions of media and digital competencies, making it difficult to create research tools

Selection of Indicators

It is difficult to create a full range of indicators that cover all aspects of digital and media competencies.

One-dimensional Measurement

Measurement often overlooks the full picture by focusing solely on the positive or negative aspects of ICT use, missing both the opportunities and risks of digitalisation.

Measurement Scales

Measurement scales, especially those based on self-evaluation, do not always accurately reflect actual ICT proficiency levels.

Challenges of Research Tool Design (2/2)

Subjectivity of Measurement

Self-evaluation of digital and media competencies can lead to inaccurate results due to the Dunning-Kruger phenomenon.

Non-standardised Tools

Creating tools *_ad hoc_* can lead to methodological chaos. Too many diverse tests make comparisons impossible, so it makes sense to choose proven measurement standards.

Indiscriminate Use of Tools

There is a risk of using tools with low levels of reliability, relevance and internal consistency.

Lack of Alignment with Profession

Measurement tools should be tailored to the specifics of the group being studied, e.g., by linking research questions to the needs that new technologies meet.

Longitudinal Studies

Longitudinal analyses using standardized tools are essential for tracking changes over time.

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Section 4: Unpacking the Insights

How Do You Analyse the Results?

Now comes the time to analyse what you have gathered. In this section, we unpack both quantitative and qualitative data to reveal the insights that will shape your understanding of the intervention's effectiveness. It is about finding meaning in the numbers and stories.

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Approaches to Data Analysis

Data Collection & Analysis

- **Multi-method approach:** Collecting **quantitative & qualitative data** using various instruments
- **Analysis phases:**
 - Quantitative analysis
 - Qualitative analysis
 - Mixed-methods analysis
- **Flexible data treatment:**
 - Data **collected qualitatively** but analysed **both quantitatively & qualitatively**
 - Data **collected via both methods**

Ensuring Reliability & Validity of Data

Quantitative research

Reliability (consistency of a measuring instrument) and Validity (the extent to which an instrument measures what it purports to measure) during construction of the tools, data collection, and analysis assessment tools:

- Internal consistency.
- Test-retest reliability (stability over time).
- Inter-rater reliability (if subjective judgments are involved).
- Content validity (adequacy and representativeness of items).
- Construct validity

Assessment tools: Cronbach's alpha, ICC, confirmatory factor analysis, exploratory factor analysis, etc.

Qualitative research

- Credibility
- Dependability
- Trustworthiness
- Transparency
- Transferability

Assessment tools: triangulation, peer checking, audit trails, thick description, etc.

Mixed-methods research

Integrates quantitative and qualitative approaches, so reliability and validity must be addressed in both paradigms.

Quantitative Data Analysis

Quantitative data are **numerical measures** such as scores and percentages and use statistics. Surveys are common measurement tools for ML&DS interventions, training, and coaching effectiveness in the form of pre-, post-, and follow-up surveys.

Quantitative Data are:

- Concise
- Provide summary information (descriptive statistics)
- Allow further analysis (inferential statistics)

Quantitative Data Analysis: Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics describe, summarise, and organise the data to make sense of it

Remember: They cannot be generalised beyond the current study.

Main approaches:

- ❑ **Average** (statistical tests: Mode, mean, and median)
- ❑ **Variation** (statistical tests: Range and standard deviation)
- ❑ **Relative position or standing** (statistical tests: Percentile rank (%), and z scores)
- ❑ **Relationship** (statistical test: Correlation)
- ❑ **Frequency distribution** (as a statistical test)

Quantitative Data Analysis: Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics

enable researchers to extrapolate the meaning of their results beyond the dataset to a specific population from which the sample is drawn (**generalisability**).

Inference in statistics relies on **probability**, which measures how likely an event is to occur. It helps researchers assess whether observed relationships are genuine or due to chance. A key concept in statistical analysis is $p < .05$, indicating statistical significance. This suggests that there is less than a 5% probability that the observed result is due to random chance, assuming the null hypothesis is true.

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Understanding Parameter Estimates & Hypothesis Testing

Parameter estimates: involve studying the entire population using data from a random sample.

Estimation can be:

- Point estimation (a single value)
- Interval estimation (a range of values).
- Confidence intervals indicate a range within which the estimated parameter is believed to lie.
- Confidence levels represent the probability (%) that the estimated point falls within the specified range.
- Margin of error refers to the variability of the estimated point, expressed as $\pm Y$.

Hypothesis testing: involves using sample data to make generalisations about a population and get a statistic (fact) from a sample.

Key concepts:

- Causation and association
- Levels of significance (p-value)
- Null and research hypotheses
- Type I and II errors
- Statistical power
- Sample size and effect size

Parametric Statistical Tests for Group Comparisons

T-test independent

Comparing the means of two groups to see if there is a significant difference (e.g., between the intervention and control groups).

Paired t-test

Tests the mean difference between paired observations (e.g., pre and post-intervention).

Analysis of variance (ANOVA)

Comparing the means of three or more groups to understand if at least one group differs (e.g., three intervention types for ML&DS).

Repeated measures ANOVA

Comparing participants on the same measure at multiple time points (e.g., pre- and post-intervention, as well as during follow-ups).

Choosing the Right Statistical Test

Non-parametric statistical tests: when standard assumptions (e.g., normal distribution, interval data, large sample size) don't hold, such as with non-normal data, ordinal variables, or small sample sizes.

Which test to use?

- **Comparing two independent groups?** → Use **Mann-Whitney U test** (instead of an independent t-test).
- **Comparing two related (paired) samples?** → Use **Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test** (instead of a paired t-test).
- **Comparing more than two independent groups?** → Use **Kruskal-Wallis H test** (instead of One-Way ANOVA).
- **Comparing repeated measures within the same group?** → Use **Friedman test** (instead of repeated-measures ANOVA).

Still unsure? Consider consulting a statistician or using software that recommends the appropriate test based on your data.

Why Sample Size Matters: Understanding Statistical Power

What is statistical power?

Statistical power tells us how many participants we need to confidently detect real differences or effects in our data.

- **Why is sample size important?**

A **small sample size** can cause problems, such as:

Missing real effects that actually exist (also called a "false negative").

- **Not being able to compare groups properly** because the data is too limited.
- **Difficulty in drawing reliable conclusions** because patterns in the data are unclear.

Bottom line:

A well-sized sample increases the **chances of finding meaningful patterns** and ensures that results are **reliable and trustworthy**.

Effect Size: Measuring the Impact of Differences & Relationships

What is effect size?

Effect size tells us **how strong** a relationship between variables is or **how big** a difference between groups is. Unlike p-values (which only tell us if a result is statistically significant), **effect size helps us understand whether the result is meaningful in real life**—for example, how much an intervention or training programme improves outcomes.

▪ Why does effect size matter?

It shows the **practical impact** of findings, not just whether an effect exists.

▪ It allows **comparisons** across studies, making research more useful.

Common effect size measures:

- **Cohen's d** → Measures the size of the difference between two groups (used for t-tests).
- **Eta-squared (η^2), Cohen's f** → Measure the impact of a factor in studies with multiple groups (used in ANOVA and repeated measures ANOVA).
- **Correlation coefficient (r)** → Measures how strongly two variables are related.

Bottom line: A larger effect size means a **stronger** and more **meaningful** difference or relationship.

Analysis Tools

- ❑ https://www.psychometrica.de/effect_size.htm
- ❑ <https://www.psychologie.hhu.de/arbeitsgruppen/allgemeine-psychologie-und-arbeitspsychologie/gpower.html>
- ❑ <https://jasp-stats.org>
- ❑ <https://www.ibm.com/spss>
- ❑ <https://www.statmodel.com/>

Qualitative Data Analysis

How Do We Collect Qualitative Data?

- ✓ We gather insights through:
 - Observations** – Watching behaviours and interactions in real settings.
 - Interviews** – One-on-one conversations (structured or open-ended) to explore personal experiences.
 - Focus Groups** – Group discussions to understand shared opinions and perspectives.
 - Case Studies** – In-depth examination of real-life situations or individuals.
 - Documents & Media** – Analysing reports, videos, photos, or written materials.

What Happens After Data Collection?

- We organize and analyse materials such as: Field notes
- Interview transcripts
- Documents & reports
- Audio & video recordings

Real-World Example: Why Qualitative Analysis Matters

Imagine you are evaluating the impact of a **digital literacy training programme** for young refugees.

- **Quantitative analysis** might show that **80%** of participants improved their test scores after the training.
- But **qualitative analysis** (through interviews and focus groups) could reveal **why** the programme worked—or didn't.

For example:

- Participants might say they **struggled with technical jargon** but learned best through **hands-on practice**.
- Some might mention **peer support as a key motivator** rather than the training itself.
- Others could express that they found **certain digital tools irrelevant** to their daily needs.
- **Without qualitative insights, you might assume the training was fully effective, missing key areas for improvement!**

Takeaway: Qualitative data provides the "**why**" and "**how**" behind the numbers, helping improve interventions, policies, and programmes based on real experiences.

How We Make Sense of Qualitative Data

Unlike numbers in quantitative research, qualitative data (e.g., interviews, observations) needs a **structured approach** to find patterns and meaning.

Common Approaches:

- **Looking for key themes** – Identifying common ideas in interviews and documents.
- **Triangulation** – Combining multiple sources (e.g., interviews + observations) to get a fuller picture.
- **Grounded theory** – Letting the data guide the development of new ideas or theories.
- **Content analysis** – Categorising and interpreting words, phrases, or visuals to find trends.

Why Does It Matter?

- ✓ Ensures findings are credible and not just based on one perspective.
- ✓ Helps turn complex stories into clear insights for action.
- ✓ Supports evidence-based decision-making in policies, programmes, and interventions.
- **Example:** If interviews reveal that young people struggle with misinformation online, analysing their responses can help **design better media literacy programmes.**

Keeping Track of Qualitative Data: First Steps

What is data logging?

After collecting interviews, focus groups, or observations, we need a **clear and organised record** of the information. This step ensures that nothing gets lost and that insights are accurately captured.

What does it involve?

- ✓ **Recording raw data** – Writing down what was said, seen, or observed.
- ✓ **Adding researcher notes** – Documenting thoughts, first impressions, and emerging ideas.
- ✓ **Revisiting the data** – Reviewing notes and transcripts to find key patterns and insights.

Why is this step important?

- Ensures that all voices and perspectives are captured.
- Helps researchers identify important themes early on.
- Creates a structured foundation for further analysis.

- **Example:** When studying digital literacy among teenagers, keeping detailed records of interviews and observations helps track how young people describe their online experiences and identify common challenges they face.

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Turning Data into Stories: Using Anecdotes

Anecdotes help transform raw data (like interviews and observations) into **meaningful stories** that capture key themes and experiences. Instead of listing facts, this step organizes information in a **narrative format**, making it easier to see patterns and insights.

How are anecdotes created?

- ✓ **Summarising interview responses** in a clear, logical order.
- ✓ **Capturing real-life experiences** shared by participants.
- ✓ **Adding context** using observations, researcher notes, or even photos.

Why is this step important?

- Helps **identify key themes** by following a person's journey or transformation.
- Brings **data to life**, making findings relatable and easy to understand.
- Ensures the research **captures emotions, motivations, and real experiences**.

➤ **Example:** If studying how people adopt digital tools, an anecdote might describe how an older adult first struggled with online banking but gradually became confident after guided training. This personal story illustrates the broader trend of digital adaptation.

Vignettes: Bringing Research to Life through Stories

Vignettes are **short, story-like descriptions** that capture key insights from research. They go beyond anecdotes by providing a **detailed and structured narrative**, helping to illustrate complex issues in a clear and engaging way.

How are vignettes used?

- ✓ **Describe real-life situations** – Who was involved? What happened? What was the context?
- ✓ **Summarise key themes** – Highlight important patterns in the data.
- ✓ **Ensure credibility** – Provide enough depth for readers to assess the findings.

Why are vignettes important?

- Make research findings relatable and easy to understand.
- Help identify deeper meanings and themes.
- Allow insights to be applied to similar real-world situations.
 - **Example:** In a study on digital literacy, a vignette might describe how a teenager learns to identify fake news online—detailing their thought process, struggles, and final realisation. This personal story illustrates broader trends in media literacy and helps readers connect with the findings.

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Data Coding: Organising Information to Find Meaning

Data coding is the process of **labelling and organising** qualitative data (like interview transcripts or field notes) to uncover key themes and patterns. It helps researchers make sense of large amounts of information by **sorting data into meaningful categories**.

How does it work?

- ✓ **Identify key topics** – Look for repeated ideas, phrases, or themes in the data.
- ✓ **Label (code) the content** – Assign short descriptions (codes) to group similar ideas together.
- ✓ **Organize and connect themes** – Use a coding framework to see relationships between concepts.

Types of coding:

- **Open coding** – Finding important words, phrases, or concepts in the data.
- **Axial coding** – Connecting related themes to see how they interact.

Why is this step important?

- Helps **turn raw data into structured insights**.
- Makes it easier to **identify patterns and relationships**.
- Provides a **clear foundation for reporting findings**.

➤ **Example:** In a study on online misinformation, open coding might highlight words like "trust," "fake news," and "social media." Axial coding would then link these themes, showing how trust in media affects the spread of misinformation.

Thematic Networks: Connecting Ideas

A thematic network organises similar codes into **broader themes** to help researchers understand the bigger picture in their data. Instead of just listing topics, this step **connects different themes** to show how they relate to each other.

Types of themes:

- **Ordinary Themes** – Expected patterns researchers anticipate finding.
- **Unexpected Themes** – Surprising insights that emerge during analysis.
- **Hard-to-Classify Themes** – Ideas that overlap with multiple themes.
- **Major Themes** – The most important, overarching ideas in the data.
- **Minor Themes** – Smaller, supporting ideas that contribute to major themes.

How are themes connected?

- ✓ **Layering the analysis** – Moving from specific details to bigger concepts.
- ✓ **Organising data into levels** – Minor themes support major themes, which then lead to broader themes.
- ✓ **Going beyond listing themes** – Showing how themes interact and contribute to a deeper understanding.

Why is this step important?

- Helps make **complex data easier to interpret**.
- **Connects smaller ideas to larger themes (clarity!).**
- Strengthens research by **moving beyond surface-level findings**.

➤ **Example:** In a study on **digital privacy concerns**, minor themes like *"data tracking,"* or *"online ads,"* could come together under the major theme *"public anxiety about online surveillance."*

Quantitative Analysis vs Qualitative Analysis

Category	Quantitative Research	Qualitative Research
Reality	Exists independently from the researcher	Is influenced by the researcher
Interaction with research object	Low, objective	High, subjective
Research questions aim on	Quantitative answers, numerical change, relationships between variables, testing hypotheses	In-depth information, developing hypotheses and theories, meaning of situations
Research design	Descriptive or causal	Exploratory, descriptive, or causal
Data collected	Numerical	Non-numerical (opinions, feelings, words)
Data analysis	Mathematically based (statistics)	Abstracting, comparing, coding, memoing, content analysis, grounded theory, hermeneutics
Interpretation/conclusions	Deductive	Inductive

Analysis Tools:

- <https://www.dedoose.com/>
- <https://lumivero.com/products/nvivo/>

Why Use Mixed Methods? Gaining a Fuller Perspective

A mixed methods study involves the collection or analysis of both **quantitative** and **qualitative data** carried out either concurrently or sequentially in a single study with some attempts to integrate the two approaches at one or more stages of the research process.

Benefits of Mixed Methods Research

Using both **quantitative (numbers)** and **qualitative (stories & experiences)** data helps create a **more complete and reliable** understanding of a topic.

- ✓ **Achieves a fuller understanding** – Combines numbers with context for deeper insights.
- ✓ **Triangulates findings** – Cross-checks results using multiple data sources for accuracy.
- ✓ **Provides illustrative insights** – Uses real-world examples to explain trends in data.
- ✓ **Offers a concise summary** – Gives a clear, well-rounded overview of findings.
- ✓ **Guides further analysis** – Provides a foundation for deeper exploration.
- ✓ **Increases Credibility** – Strengthens conclusions by integrating multiple perspectives.

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Mixed-Methods Research: Four Core Designs for Data Integration

When designing a mixed methods study, it is essential to consider your research approach, research questions, and available data. Consider how you can use various techniques to integrate the data to answer your research question.

Convergent parallel
data collection and analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data occur simultaneously.

Embedded design
The quantitative and qualitative data are collected simultaneously, but the qualitative data is embedded within the quantitative data. This design is best used when you want to focus on the quantitative data but still need to understand how the qualitative data further explains it.

Explanatory sequential design
quantitative data is collected first, followed by qualitative data. This design is used when you want to further explain a set of quantitative data with additional qualitative information

Exploratory sequential design
collects qualitative data first, followed by quantitative data. This type of mixed methods research is used when the goal is to explore a topic before collecting any quantitative data.

Beyond the Basics: Advanced Mixed-Methods Research Designs

Multistage

This framework mixes qualitative and quantitative data collection methods in stages to gather a more nuanced view of the research question. An example of this is a study that first has an online survey to collect initial data and is followed by in-depth interviews to gain further insights.

Intervention

This design involves collecting quantitative data and then taking action, usually in the form of an intervention or intervention program.

Case study

This utilizes both qualitative and quantitative research methods to analyze a single case. The researcher will examine the specific case in detail to understand the factors influencing it.

Participatory

This type of research focuses on the involvement of participants in the research process. It involves the active participation of participants in formulating and developing research questions, data collection, and analysis.

An example of this could be a study that involves forming focus groups with participants who actively develop the research questions and then provide feedback during the data collection and analysis stages.

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Integrating Data in Mixed-Methods Research

A crucial step that enhances analysis depth and strengthens research credibility. Below are three key integration techniques:

1. Triangulation Protocol

- ✓ Combines multiple methods to compare and synthesize differing or conflicting results.
- ✓ Produces a more comprehensive conclusion.

2. Following a Thread

- ✓ Identifies a central theme and traces it across different data collection phases.
- **Example:** A study may start with **quantitative data**, followed by **qualitative research** to explore underlying explanations.

3. Mixed-Methods Matrix

- ✓ A visual tool for mapping research designs and implementation sequences.
- ✓ Helps researchers assess and refine their approach.
- ✓ Includes four designs: **Convergent Parallel, Explanatory Sequential, Exploratory Sequential, and Method Flexibility.**

Further Reading & Resources

- Zohrabi, M. (2013). Vu, T. T. N. (2021). Understanding validity and reliability from qualitative and quantitative research traditions. *VNU Journal of Foreign Studies*, 37(3).
- Creswell, J., & Poth, C. (2013). *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches* (4th ed.). SAGE.
- Mixed method research: Instruments, validity, reliability and reporting findings. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 3(2), 254-262.
- McGregor, S. (2018). Descriptive and inferential statistics in Understanding and Evaluating Research: A Critical Guide (Vol. 0, pp. 309-344). SAGE.
- O’Cathain, A., Murphy, E., & Nicholl, J. (2010). Three techniques for integrating data in mixed methods studies. *Bmj*, 341.
- Akinyode, B. F., & Khan, T. H. (2018). Step by step approach for qualitative data analysis. *International Journal of Built Environment and Sustainability*, 5(3).

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Ethical & Data Protection Guidance

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Understanding Data Categories & Processing

It is essential to recognise that different **categories of data** require distinct processing methods. These categories influence how data are **collected, stored, analysed, and protected** throughout the research process.

Topics covered in this section include:

- **Data classification & sensitivity** – Understanding different types of data (e.g., personal, sensitive, anonymised) and their implications.
- **Informed consent & participant rights** – Ethical considerations when collecting and using participant data.
- **Data storage & security** – Best practices for safeguarding data integrity and confidentiality.
- **Data sharing & transparency** – Guidelines for responsible data sharing while maintaining privacy and ethical standards.
- **Regulatory compliance** – Adhering to GDPR, institutional policies, and other relevant data protection laws.

Categories of Data

Collected Data

Gathered data through qualitative and quantitative methods, such as surveys, interviews, and observations.

Produced data

Produced during the evaluation process
E.g., survey results, interview transcriptions, analysis codes, and algorithms.

Produced/collected data

e.g., consents, agreements, contracts.

Personal Data: Direct & Indirect Identifiers

Understanding **direct, strong indirect, and indirect identifiers** is essential for ensuring **proper data handling, privacy protection, and compliance with ethical and legal standards**:

- a. **Direct identifiers:** Information that can uniquely identify an individual includes a person's name, email address, identification number, fingerprints, facial images, voice recordings, videos.
- b. **Strong indirect identifiers:** Information that can easily identify an individual, such as postal address, phone number, student ID number, IP address, cookie identifier, location data.
- c. **Indirect identifiers:** Information that, when combined with other data, can help identify an individual. Examples include age, gender, education, ethnic background, postal code, and region.

Source: Enrico Glerean/Aalto Open Science team

Personal Data Protection

In research involving human participants, distinguishing between **minimisation**, **pseudonymisation**, and **anonymisation** is essential to ensure **ethical data handling**, **privacy protection**, and **regulatory compliance**:

- ✓ **Minimisation:** The minimum amount of personal data necessary to accomplish a task should be collected.
- ✓ **Pseudonymisation:** Replacement of identifiers with pseudonyms or codes, which are kept separately and protected by technical and organizational measures
- ✓ **Anonymisation:** removing the link between data and its subject, ensuring that no one can easily restore this connection.

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Source: [EU GDPR, Recital 26](#)

Personal Data Protection: Participants' Rights (1/2)

Consent: Under data protection legislation, subjects (guardians with children and adolescent participants) must always be asked to give their consent for the collection and processing of personal data (GDPR consent).

Source: Irani et al. (2024) →

Participant's Consent

I have read and understood the information sheet provided to me. I am familiar with the purpose and content of this research, the use of the research data collected, the potential risks to participants, as well as the rights of participants and insurance coverage. I have had sufficient time to consider participating in the research. I have had the opportunity to ask questions and have received answers to all my questions regarding the research.

I agree to participate in this research voluntarily and understand that I can withdraw at any time without affecting my treatment. Individual participants will not be identifiable in the results. I can withdraw my consent after the research concludes if personal data processing continues. If I discontinue participation instead of withdrawing consent, the data collected up to that point may still be used.

I understand that the information collected during the research will be handled confidentially and will not be disclosed to third parties. The research results and collected data may be used in a form in which individual participants cannot be identified. I may be contacted later if needed in relation to the research. With my consent, the collected learning data may be stored long-term in an anonymized form and used later as part of broader research using a similar experimental setup.

Based on the criteria described in this consent form and the participant information sheet, I am eligible to participate in this research.

By signing below, I provide my informed consent to participate in this research.

Participant Information

Name: _____
Date of Birth: _____
Address: _____
Signature: _____
Date: ____ / ____ / ____

Researcher's Declaration

I have explained this research to the participant in accordance with the information sheet, and I confirm that they understand their involvement in this research.

Researcher's Name: _____
Signature: _____
Date: ____ / ____ / ____

Participation is voluntary & right to refuse to participate

Right to withdraw consent to participation

Content and implementation of the study

Objectives of the study & related harms & risks

Processing of personal data

Researcher's roles (if more than one)

Source:
University of Helsinki Data Support

Personal Data Protection: Participants' Rights (2/2)

Informing: Informing should be done before or during the data collection and should be understandable, without jargon, and unambiguous.

Note: informing and consent are not synonymous!

Source: [University of Helsinki Data Support](#)

Information Sheet

Title of Study:

Information about the Study and Procedures

This study aims to understand the impact of media literacy and digital skills (ML&DS) interventions in various life domains. It focuses on fostering positive outcomes such as informed decision-making, civic engagement, and online safety. Media literacy refers to the capacity to access, analyze, evaluate, and create media content, while digital skills encompass the ability to use digital devices, platforms, and tools effectively.

This research seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of ML&DS interventions by assessing participants' abilities to critically analyze digital content, engage with media platforms responsibly, and safeguard against misinformation. Participation in this evaluation will involve evaluating digital media content, completing questionnaires, and reflecting on your digital experiences. The entire process will take approximately 2 hours.

Suitability for Participation

Participants should have internet access on a computer or mobile device. This study is open to individuals from various backgrounds, and participation is entirely voluntary. Please contact the research team if you have any concerns regarding your suitability for the study.

Preparation for participation

Participation does not require specific preparation. The evaluation will involve analyzing media messages, critically assessing news articles and social media content, and answering questions about digital safety and misinformation.

Contact for Further Information

If you have any questions or require further information about this study, please contact [Researcher's Name] at [Contact Details].

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Data Agreements & Sharing

- ❑ **Joint Controller Agreement (JCA)** is required when two or more organisations jointly process data (collaborative research), i.e. they jointly define the purposes and means of the processing.
- ❑ **Data Processing Agreement (DPA)** is necessary if the personal data is processed by a data processor, i.e. a service provider who processes the data on behalf of research team.
- ❑ **Standard contractual clauses (SCC)** may be required when personal data are transferred or processed outside the EU/EEA, i.e., the controller or processor is located outside the EU/EEA. This agreement is required in addition to the DPA, JCA.
- ❑ In the context of a research consortium in which another university creates data, it is essential to establish clear agreements regarding data usage and ownership. Key considerations include identifying the data owner and defining the terms under which the data may be used.

Source: [University of Helsinki Data Support](#)

Data Storage & Security

Considerations for Data Management

- Proper data description
- Required storage space.
- Software to process the data
- Access to the data and sharing it
- The whole lifecycle of the data, including long-term plans
- Available budget
- Low, medium and high-risk data

Data type	Source of the data	File Format	Size estimate	Sensitivity / Personal data + controller	Owner / other agreements?	Documentation	Storage during project	Opening	Long term archiving
1									
2									
3									
4									
5									
6									
7									
8									
9									
10									
11									

Further Reading & Resources

- When is the processing of personal data permitted?
<https://tietosuoja.fi/en/when-is-the-processing-of-personal-data-permitted>
- Anonymization and personal data (the Finnish Social Science Data archive)
<https://www.fsd.tuni.fi/en/services/data-management-guidelines/anonymisation-and-identifiers/>
- Short and informative guidelines from the UK Data Service:
<https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/learning-hub/research-data-management>
- Guide for data documentation:
<https://zenodo.org/records/1914401>

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Section 5: Telling the Story and Making It Better

How Do You Report and Improve?

Reporting is not just about presenting data – it is about telling the whole story of the intervention, including successes, challenges, and lessons learned. The key to effective reporting is transparency, clarity, and that it resonates with stakeholders.

Reporting & Dissemination Guidelines

In addition to carrying out the evaluation and analysing the data, it is important to share the results within your organisation and with relevant stakeholders.

There are three basic guidelines for reporting and dissemination:

- 1. Write an evaluation report:**
Share your findings by putting together a clear, accurate and compelling Evaluation report.
- 2. Tailor findings to stakeholders:**
Different audiences (i.e., policymakers, academics, other practitioners, the public) are interested in different things: Consider your audience's knowledge needs while planning your evaluation report.
- 3. Disseminate the results:**
Plan your communication and share your story internally and externally for letting your organisation and others learn from your experiences.

Evaluation Report: Clarity & Transparency

An evaluation report summarises key findings and recommendations in a concise format tailored to the target audience.

Its purpose is to:

- present your key findings, supported by the data.
- critically reflect on the contribution of the intervention to the observed results and outcomes.
- share what you have learned so that others can benefit and avoid making the same mistakes.

Its purpose is NOT to:

- make the intervention appear more successful than it was by presenting only the positive outcomes and omitting the negative ones.
- Overstate the intervention's contribution to the outcome, disregarding the potential influence of other factors.

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3.2. Selecting the
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3.3. Evaluation
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3.4. Intervention
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4. Unpacking the
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4.1. Data Analysis

4.2. Ethical & Data
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5. Telling the Story

5.1. Reporting &
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6. Continuous
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8. Useful Resources

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Evaluation Report: Where to Start?

You can start writing the report once:

- the data are collected and analysed.
- you have identified your audience, their interests, and the purpose of the results for them.
- you have a **software** or a **template** for designing your work and visualising your data.
 - The report can take many forms: a written report, slide presentation and/or webpages.
 - Range of templates and tools can be used for designing the report.

Tools and templates to get you started:

Microsoft Office (Word, PowerPoint, Excel etc.)

diverse tools for written report and slides.

Survey Monkey - dashboard can also be used for reporting.

Canva - design software with available report templates.

Evaluation Report: Structure & Contents

Regardless of the format, it is recommended to include the following parts in the evaluation report:

- **Executive summary:**
1-2 p. summary of your key findings and recommendations
- **Introduction:**
A brief description of what you are evaluating; some background information of the intervention; aims and purposes of the evaluation; theory of change
- **Evaluation aims and scope:**
Evaluation questions, general overview of the research methodology
- **Findings:**
Key results, outcomes, and impacts
- **Limitations and challenges:**
e.g., data size, generalisability, other issues
- **Recommendations:**
What went well, what could be improved in future interventions
- **Appendix:**
Details of your project and data collection delivery

Tailoring Findings to Stakeholders

Rather than using a 'one-size-fits-all' approach, it is more effective to tailor different versions of the report for various stakeholders.

1. Who is your intended audience and what are their interests?

Other practitioners might be more interested in knowing the details of your intervention and data gathering (what you did and how), whereas funders might be more interested in impact metrics.

2. What key numbers your audience needs to know?

Numbers or percentages; total results or comparisons between different groups

3. Visualise your data

Use visuals (diagrams, graphs, charts, quotations) to highlight the most important findings.

4. Check data anonymity and consent of your participants

Make sure your participants cannot be recognised from the data without their consent.

5. Be transparent: minimize bias when reporting your results

Be open about the limitations of your data and results.

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Section 6: Continuous Improvement & Sustainability

**How can you bring together
improvement and sustainability?**

Continuous Improvement helps interventions evolve over time, while **sustainability** ensures long-term resources and impact. Together, they keep interventions flexible and successful.

A **Monitoring & Evaluation Plan** tracks progress and refines strategies, while the **Review & Revision Process** keeps interventions aligned with objectives through regular assessments.

Designing & Implementing Your Monitoring & Evaluation Plan

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Introduction to a Monitoring & Evaluation Plan

A Monitoring & Evaluation Plan (M&E Plan) is essential for tracking progress, assessing impact, and improving strategies.

Think of it as a roadmap: starting with clear objectives, guiding data collection, structuring analysis, and ensuring results are shared effectively.

What does it allow?

Importance of Monitoring & Evaluation Plan

Why is a Monitoring & Evaluation Plan Important?

1. Ensures **transparency and accountability** by tracking processes and aligning activities with objectives.
2. Allows for **real-time adjustments** based on monitoring data and feedback.
3. Strengths collaboration among stakeholders, including funders, teams, and beneficiaries.
4. Provides **evidence-based results** that demonstrate the intervention's impact and improve its effectiveness.

Before continuing (...)

A well-designed Monitoring & Evaluation Plan keeps interventions dynamic, effective, and aligned with programme objectives and beneficiaries' needs. By combining continuous monitoring with impact evaluation, it helps optimise resources and results.

Structure of Your M&E Plan

Designing your M&E Plan

- Intervention characteristics are key to design your M&E Plan
- Evaluation planning, essential in the design phase (*aspects to evaluate, data collection methods, the sample, evaluation timing, data analysis methods, success indicators*)

Implementing your M&E Plan

- Real-time monitoring
- Evaluation of intermediate results
- Adjustments during the intervention
- Continuous feedback

Before continuing (...)

Keep in mind the ToC before designing and implementing your M&E Plan! And remember that It is crucial to distinguish between **Monitoring**

(tracking if activities are implemented effectively) and **Evaluation** (assessing the achieved impact) to optimise results.

Reporting and Dissemination

- Analysis of results
- Writing down the results (reporting)
- Sharing results
- Using results

Practical Function

- Continuous monitoring ensures that activities are being carried out as planned.
- Final evaluation measures the intervention's impact and whether the objectives were achieved.

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A solid M&E Plan
makes interventions
more effective

Designing Your Monitoring & Evaluation Plan

Three Key Questions to Design Your M&E Plan (1/3)

1. What to evaluate?

(1) Actions

Define the specific activities to achieve the objectives

For example: Workshops for teachers to identify misinformation

(2) Processes

Assess how activities are delivered to ensure quality

For example: Interactive, hybrid formats tailored to participant needs

(3) Outcomes

Measure the impact to confirm success and inform improvements

For example: Increased critical thinking through pre- and post-tests

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- ✓ ***Understanding what to evaluate ensures clarity in goals and alignment with the intervention's purpose***

Three Key Questions to Design Your M&E Plan (2/3)

2. Why set clear objectives and identify problems?

Objectives give direction and allow tracking progress

For example: Enhance digital skills of NEETs by 30% in six months

Identifying problems ensures the intervention addresses real needs

For example: Bridging digital inclusion gaps among vulnerable groups

- ✓ **Clear objectives guide the intervention's focus and ensure measurable progress**

A well-designed Monitoring & Evaluation Plan ensures structured data collection, analysis, and reporting, keeping the intervention on track.

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Three Key Questions to Design Your M&E Plan (3/3)

3. Do you know your beneficiaries?

Why is it important?

Knowing your target groups ensures relevance and impact.

Tailored activities maximise engagement and outcomes:

For example: Teachers require tools to tackle misinformation, while elderly people need foundational digital skills.

Before continuing (...)

SMART Objectives

Objectives must be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and time-bound to provide a clear direction and ensure progress tracking.

Theory of Change (ToC)

Linking each activity to expected outcomes ensures the intervention aligns with its goals and achieves the desired impact.

Characteristics for M&E Design Plan

Intervention Characteristics & M&E Design Plan (1/5)

1. Who is implementing the intervention?

- **The type of organisation** influences the approach and available **resources**, directly shaping monitoring and evaluation strategies.

For example: Academia, NGOs, Government, Private Companies.

2. What approach are you going to use?

- The approach defines the programme's framework and the type of activities to be carried out. This is crucial for determining what is being measured (e.g., **digital skills or media literacy**).

For example: Media literacy, digital skills, or a combination of both.

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Intervention Characteristics & M&E Design Plan (2/5)

3. What areas does your intervention address?

- The intervention's **focus** determines the metrics for evaluation and how they align with expected outcomes
For example: Online safety, content creation, critical thinking, etc.

4. What clear and measurable objectives does your intervention have?

- **SMART** objectives serve as the foundation for evaluation indicators and ensure alignment with the programme's goals.
For example: Increase teachers' digital skills by 20% by the end of the programme.

Before continuing (...)

*Understanding **key characteristics of the intervention** ensures that monitoring and evaluation plan is aligned with intervention's goals and activities.*

Intervention Characteristics & M&E Design Plan (3/5)

5. What is the educational format of your intervention?

- The **modality** affects the type of tools and methods needed for evaluation.
For example: Online, in-person, or hybrid (combination of online and in-person).

6. How will the programme be delivered?

- The way **participation** is facilitated influences the type of interaction and engagement from beneficiaries.
For example: Live classes, autonomous learning, group activities.

Intervention Characteristics & M&E Design Plan (4/5)

7. How long will your intervention last?

- **Duration and frequency** are essential for planning when evaluations will take place (pre-, intermediate, post-intervention).

For example: A six-month intervention with weekly 2-hour sessions.

8. Who is going to deliver the activities?

- **Facilitators** play a crucial role in the success of the intervention.
- Their performance and interaction with participants should be assessed.

For example: Trainers, subject matter experts, researchers.

Intervention Characteristics & M&E Design Plan (5/5)

9. Who are the beneficiaries and what is their profile?

- Understanding the characteristics of the target group (age, educational level, socioeconomic context) allows for adapting activities and evaluation methods to meet their specific needs
For example: Secondary school students, teachers, older adults, vulnerable groups.

Before continuing (...)

These characteristics provide a clear framework for aligning evaluation activities with the specific goals, resources, and context of the intervention.

*By addressing aspects such as **educational modality, participation methods, duration, and target audience**, you can ensure that the intervention is both impactful and adaptable to the needs of its beneficiaries.*

Integrating Evaluation into M&E Design

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Evaluation Planning: Steps for Success

Is it clear to you how the evaluation process works?

Evaluation planning involves:

1. Identifying **which aspects to evaluate**
2. Selecting appropriate **methods for data collection**
3. Defining **the sample** to ensure the results are representative and reliable
4. Setting up the **evaluation timing**
5. Choosing the **data analysis** methods
6. Defining the success **indicators**

Before continuing (...)

Evaluation planning is a key step to ensure that an intervention achieves its intended goals and generates measurable impact

Evaluation Planning (1/6)

1. Is it clear which aspects you are going to evaluate?

Knowledge

What knowledge have participants acquired?

Skills

What skills have participants learned or practiced?

Behaviour

Has there been a change in beneficiaries' behavior regarding the use of technology?

Retention

What knowledge has been retained over time?

Clarifying what to evaluate ensures alignment with intervention goals and focuses on the most relevant outcomes.

Evaluation Planning (2/6)

2. Have you clearly identified the data collection methods you are going to use?

Pre- and post-tests

Evaluate knowledge or skills before and after the intervention

Surveys

Gather participants' perceptions about the intervention

Interviews

Conduct an in-depth exploration of participants' experiences

Focus groups

Collect qualitative feedback through group discussions

Direct observation

Monitor participants' behaviour during intervention activities

Choosing the right methods ensures the evaluation generates accurate and actionable insights.

Evaluation Planning (3/6)

3. Have you clearly defined the sample design and size?

Sampling strategies ensure the evaluation captures diverse perspectives and provides reliable results

Random sampling

Randomly selecting participants to obtain a representative sample.

Convenience sampling

Selecting participants who are readily available or willing to participate.

Specific characteristics

Choosing participants with specific criteria (e.g., level of digital literacy).

Defining a clear sample strategy ensures the evaluation reflects diverse perspectives and provides reliable results.

Evaluation Planning (4/6)

4. Have you defined your evaluation timing?

The main phases are:

Before

Assess initial levels of knowledge and skills

During

Measure progress and identify real-time issues

After

Evaluate the overall impact and final results of the intervention

Before continuing (...)

A comprehensive evaluation plan aligns the intervention's objectives with actionable insights that drive continuous improvement and scalability.

Breaking the evaluation process into distinct phases ensures that progress is tracked and challenges are addressed effectively throughout the intervention.

Evaluation Planning (5/6)

5. Have you defined the data analysis method?

Qualitative

Interviews and focus groups capture detailed feedback and perceptions.

Quantitative

Surveys and pre-/post-tests measure numerical changes.

Data analysis is the process of examining, organising, and interpreting data to extract meaningful insights.

By combining qualitative and quantitative methods, you can gain a deeper understanding of the intervention's effectiveness and identify areas for improvement.

Evaluation Planning (6/6)

6. Have you established precise success indicators?

Qualitative

Subjective but valuable insights, like improved confidence or satisfaction reported by participants

Quantitative

Clearly measurable outcomes, such as a 25% of participants increased their digital use

Indicators are metrics used to measure the achievement of objectives and the impact of the intervention.

Implementing your Monitoring & Evaluation Plan Continuous Analysis & Improvement

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Continuous Monitoring & Improvement

Successful intervention implementation requires **ongoing monitoring and flexibility** to **make adjustments** when necessary.

Continuous feedback helps **identify challenges, adapt to unexpected outcomes,** and ensure **alignment with the intervention's objectives.**

The use of **appropriate monitoring tools** supports **informed decision-making** and fosters **ongoing improvement** throughout the process.

We need to remember 4 key components:

1. **Real-time monitoring**
2. **Evaluation of intermediate results**
3. **Adjustments during the intervention**
4. **Continuous feedback**

1. Real-Time Monitoring

How will continuous monitoring be carried out?

Digital tools

Use monitoring platforms to track the progress of activities.

For example: Platforms like Trello or Asana can help manage and follow task progress.

Regular surveys

Collect feedback from participants at regular intervals during the intervention.

For example: Mid-session satisfaction surveys to measure perceptions and engagement.

Direct observation

Observe activities to ensure they are conducted as planned.

For example: Supervisors or facilitators attending live sessions and taking notes on student participation.

Real-time monitoring ensures that activities are on track and progress is regularly assessed.

2. Intermediate Results Evaluation

What results will be evaluated during the intervention?

Ongoing evaluation

Conduct mid-course evaluations to assess intervention progress.

For example: Administer skills tests midway through the programme to see if participants are progressing as expected.

Problem identification

Detect potential challenges or deviations from the original plan.

For example: If a group of participants is not progressing, identify barriers and adapt accordingly.

Intermediate evaluations measure progress and identify potential issues and barriers during implementation.

3. Adjustment During the Intervention

How and when should adjustments be made?

Based on monitoring data

Use monitoring results to make adjustments during the process.

For example: Modify or change the focus of an activity if survey or observation data show it is not working.

Stakeholder involvement

Keep key stakeholders (facilitators, administrators, funders) informed of any changes.

For example: If a programme change is made, communicate it to all stakeholders to ensure alignment with the new plans.

Decisions based on evidence ensure the intervention remains effective and aligned with its goals.

4. Feedback

How can feedback be effectively collected and used?

Continuous feedback collection

Encourage participants, facilitators, and stakeholders to provide ongoing feedback.

For example: Schedule weekly feedback sessions to evaluate course progress and identify areas for improvement.

Continuous improvement culture

Create an environment where feedback is valued and actively used to refine activities.

For example: Conduct quick evaluations after each module or activity and discuss potential improvements.

Regular feedback from participants, facilitators, and stakeholders helps the intervention adapt and improve over time.

Reporting & Dissemination Analysis of Results & Communication Strategies

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Analysis of Results & Communication Strategies

Before starting (...)

A clear strategy is essential to analyse the results of the intervention, communicate its impact, and share lessons learned with stakeholders.

This includes:

1. **Analysis of results**
2. **Writing down your results (reporting)**
3. **Sharing results**
4. **Using results**

Ensuring your results reach the right audiences is key to improving future interventions and achieving meaningful outcomes.

1. Analysis of Results

How will the collected data be analysed?

Quantitative analysis

Use statistical methods to interpret numerical results (e.g., increase in digital skills).

For example: Compare pre- and post-test results to measure improvements in competencias

Qualitative analysis

Analyse interviews, open-ended survey responses, and focus groups to understand participant experiences and perceptions.

For example: Examine feedback on the quality and applicability of the training content.

Analysing data is crucial to understanding the effectiveness of the intervention, identifying areas for improvement, and ensuring that the results provide actionable insights for future strategies.

2. Writing Down Your Results (Reporting)

How can you write down your results in a final report?

What to include?

Executive summary

A concise overview of the objectives, methodology, key results, and overall impact

Detailed analysis

A thorough presentation of quantitative and qualitative data, showing how results align with the intervention's objectives

Recommendations

Suggestions for improving future interventions based on findings

Lessons learned

Reflections on challenges encountered and how they were addressed

A final report can compare the intervention's results to initial expectations and propose adjustments for the next iteration.

3. Sharing Results

How will the results be shared?

Presentations to stakeholders

Organize presentations to share results with funders, collaborators, and key stakeholders

Written report

Prepare a detailed report for involved parties and share it digitally

Data visualization

Use graphs, dashboards, and executive summaries to simplify the understanding of results

Public dissemination

Publish findings on websites, newsletters, or social media to increase visibility

Before continuing (...)

Effectively sharing and using the results of an intervention is essential for improving future efforts and keeping stakeholders informed.

A clear strategy helps make the most of the findings and guides the planning of future initiatives.

A clear communication strategy ensures that results are effectively delivered to stakeholders.

4. Using Results

How will the results be used?

Future improvements

Use the results to adjust future interventions and improve teaching methods or activities.

Academic and social dissemination

Leverage findings to publish articles, present at conferences, and share knowledge with the community

Transparency

Ensure funders and stakeholders receive the necessary information about resource use and achieved outcomes.

Findings are essential for improving future interventions and ensuring transparency.

Review & Revision Process based on M&E Plan Ensuring Effectiveness & Flexibility

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Ensuring Effectiveness & Flexibility

Reviewing results regularly, monitoring methods, and evaluation practices is essential to ensure that the intervention meets its objectives.

The review process must remain flexible to adapt the intervention based on feedback and data collected during implementation.

This iterative and collaborative process ensures that all necessary adjustments are made effectively and on time.

We need to remember six steps:

1. **The importance of continuous review**
2. **When to conduct reviews?**
3. **Who** should be involved in the review process?
4. **Making adjustments based on reviews**
5. **Documenting** adjustments
6. **Communication and feedback** on reviews

The Importance of Continuous Review

1. Why is it necessary to review the plan during implementation?

Adapting to unexpected changes

During implementation, unexpected situations may arise, such as shifts in context, beneficiary needs, or resource availability.

Ensuring effectiveness

Feedback and monitoring results may indicate the need for adjustments to improve activities.

For example: If monitoring reveals technical difficulties with digital tools, the plan should be adjusted to address these challenges.

Continuous reviews help adapt to unexpected changes and ensure the intervention remains effective.

When to Conduct Reviews?

2. At what stage should reviews take place?

Initial review

After the first activities or during the initial project phase to adjust the approach if needed.

Midterm review

Midway through the intervention to evaluate progress and make real-time adjustments.

Final review

At the end of the intervention to assess whether objectives were achieved and gather insights on impact.

For example: For a six-month intervention, a formal review could take place after three months to implement changes based on data collected.

Reviews should be conducted regularly at key moments throughout the intervention.

Who Should Be Involved in the Review Process?

3. Who plays a role in review decisions?

Facilitators and evaluators

Collaborate to identify necessary adjustments during implementation.

Stakeholders

Funders, programme administrators, and other key stakeholders should be consulted during reviews to align on proposed changes.

For example: If evaluators find teaching methods ineffective, they can request facilitators to adjust their approach while stakeholders review the proposed changes before implementation.

Making Adjustments Based on Reviews (1/2)

4. How to implement adjustments?

Methodology adjustments

Change teaching strategies or modify activities to enhance engagement or learning outcomes.

For example: If in-person activities are not effective, increase online engagement with interactive resources.

Content adjustments

Update programme content to ensure relevance and effectiveness based on evaluation results.

For example: If participants demonstrate mastery of a topic, move to more advanced material.

Focus adjustments

Modify the programme's general focus to better align with objectives.

For example: Shift from technical skills to critical thinking if participants require development in this area.

Making Adjustments Based on Reviews (2/2)

5. How to document adjustments?

Regular reports

Maintain detailed reports on revisions made, reasons for changes, and their impact on the monitoring and evaluation plan.

Action plans

Create a clear plan for implementing adjustments and ensure all stakeholders are informed.

For example: If teaching methodology changes, document the rationale and expected impact to track its effectiveness.

Documenting all adjustments ensures transparency, measures effectiveness, and aligns all stakeholders.

Communication & Feedback on Reviews

6. How can communication improve the review process?

Regular meetings

Schedule discussions with key stakeholders to review and refine adjustments

Open communication channels

Maintain open lines of communication between facilitators, evaluators, and stakeholders to efficiently manage changes

For example: If facilitators change the teaching method, they should inform the evaluation team and seek feedback.

Continuous review and revision ensure that the intervention stays aligned with objectives, methods remain effective, and adjustments are timely.

This iterative process fosters collaboration and involvement from all key participants.

Effective communication ensures alignment among all parties and integrates continuous feedback into the review process.

Further Reading

- [The Digital Inclusion Evaluation Toolkit: Bank of Outcomes, Indicators and Survey Questions \(Just Economics, 2017\)](#)
- [WHO Europe Guide: Media and Information Literacy for Public Health](#)
- [Ofcom Media Literacy Toolkit: Promoting Informed Media Use](#)
- [Report on the Development of the Evaluation Strategies Tailored to Media Literacy and Digital Skills Intervention Programmes](#)
- [Evaluating Twelve Media Literacy and Digital Skills Interventions](#)

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Section 7: Intervention Evaluation Recommendations

Spotlight on Diverse Audiences

Fresh insights from hands-on
empirical studies across diverse
contexts

Estonia: Spotlight on In-Service Teachers

1. Guarantee Organisational Stability

- Mitigate personnel turnover by introducing extensive handover arrangements, writing down agreements, and using shared digital platforms to ensure continuity in assessment processes.

2. Build Collaborative Partnerships

- Leverage collaborations with academic institutions and local organisations to align goals and responsibilities effectively.

3. Leverage Digital Literacy

- Leverage the high digital literacy of participants (e.g., Estonian teachers) to streamline evaluation processes and provide pre-intervention training in less digitally literate contexts.

4. Embed Evaluation into Intervention Design

- Embed evaluation activities seamlessly within intervention workflows, improving engagement and addressing disengagement caused by uncoordinated processes.

5. Extend Intervention Durations

- Design longer, multi-session interventions that would allow deeper engagement and long-term measurement of impacts, addressing the limitations brought about by short-term programs.

Estonia: Spotlight on In-Service Teachers

1. Adapt Interventions to Participants' Needs

- Adapt content to participant profiles, such as aligning workshops with teacher needs.
- Avoid standardised tools mismatched with specific context needs; develop customised instruments – shorten, adjust, and translate.

2. Improve Transparency via Better Communication

- Clearly communicate evaluation objectives, making a point that the evaluation does not target participants but interventions themselves to allow honest and participative contributions.

3. Incentivise Participation

- Provide small but meaningful incentives that align with intervention objectives to enhance motivation and relevance (e.g., USB drives, notebooks, free access to premium e-learning tools, and gift cards).

4. Leverage Cost-Free Interventions

- Keep the interventions cost-free to ensure some degree of reciprocity and continuing engagement, especially for busy respondents such as teachers.

5. Use Longitudinal Designs in Measuring Impact

- Use follow-up evaluations to determine how much actual learning is sustained when follow-up is necessary for a particular population (e.g., examine how teachers are actually implementing practices in their classrooms).

Belgium: Spotlight on Parents with Low Digital Literacy (Migration & Low-Income Backgrounds)

1. Use simple, relatable language and real-life examples

- Hands-on practice with own devices
- Structured learning: from basic skills to online privacy

2. Inclusive & Supportive Learning Environment

- Group activities & peer learning
- Translation services & co-instructors
- Flexible formats: in-person, webinars, printed guides

3. Encouraging Active Digital Mediation

- Move beyond restriction to active discussions
- Build parents' confidence in guiding children online
- Promote quality educational resources

4. Addressing Digital Literacy Gaps

- Detecting misinformation & scams
- Safe online shopping & financial security
- Handling children's exposure to harmful content

5. Engaging Fathers & Diverse Caregivers

- Gender-inclusive outreach strategies
- Workplace, community-based sessions for fathers
- Sessions for preschool educators & community workers

6. Effective Training & Evaluation

- Time management & follow-up resources
- Partnerships with local organizations
- Long-term impact assessment (6-month follow-ups)

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Spain: Spotlight on Secondary School Teachers & Students

1. Engage Non-Academic Partners Early

Involve partners throughout the design and evaluation process for relevant, context-appropriate assessment tools.

2. Adapt Evaluation to School Constraints

Use simple, digital-friendly tools integrated into teaching schedules to ease teachers' workload.

3. Clarify the Purpose of Evaluation

Assure teachers that evaluation aims to improve the programme, not assess their performance.

4. Support Sustainability with Incentives

Offer recognition, funding, or resources for non-academic partners and set clear data collection protocols.

Spain: Spotlight on Secondary School Teachers & Students

5. Give Teachers Time to Prepare

Provide preparatory sessions for teachers to familiarise themselves with materials before implementation.

6. Tailor Content to Student Diversity

Ensure flexible materials adaptable to different school contexts and student needs.

7. Use Long-Term Evaluation Strategies

Conduct follow-ups at 3, 6, and 12 months to assess knowledge retention and real impact.

*The key to success lies in **close collaboration between academic and non-academic partners, flexibility in evaluation, clear communication, and long-term sustainability.***

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Finland: Spotlight on Vocational Students & the Elderly (1/2)

1. Adapt Interventions and Materials to Participant Needs

Tailor the evaluation tool to suit the target group's competencies. For example, you can choose to print out the questionnaire for older adults or send it as a link to students.

2. Embed Evaluation into Intervention Design

At its best, evaluation can strengthen the intervention. With relevant content, pre- and post-tests can guide participants through the lessons and help them review the content.

3. Participation of Qualified Trainers and Peer Tutors

Involving experienced trainers in the planning and delivery ensures that the intervention and evaluation are well-suited to the needs of the participants.

The involvement of peer tutors can even out the differences in the skills of the participants and make it easier for them to follow the lessons.

Finland: Spotlight on Vocational Students & the Elderly (2/2)

4. **Incentivise Participation**

Minimise barriers to participation, for example by making the course free of charge or by including it in the school day.

5. **Communicate the Purpose of Evaluation Clearly and Encourage Participation**

Inform about the evaluation in advance. Especially with older adults, it is good to emphasise that the evaluation is not about the participant but about the intervention.

6. **Consider Including Different Methods in Your Evaluation**

By complementing quantitative survey data with qualitative data (interview, feedback, observation), a more comprehensive picture of the effectiveness of the intervention can be obtained.

7. **Avoid Survey Fatigue**

Keep the evaluation as light and clear as possible and limit the total amount of research activity to avoid survey fatigue.

UK: Spotlight on Low-Income & Refugee Groups

1. **Know Your Beneficiaries** – Use **pre-tests** to assess participants' **ML&DS levels** and tailor content accordingly.
2. **Adapt to Native Languages** – Provide materials in participants' **native language** when possible to **increase engagement** and remove barriers.
3. **Clarify Evaluation's Purpose** – Explain to volunteers and those implementing the evaluation how **it will or can be used to improve the intervention**, encouraging participation. **Provide feedback** including presentation of the results when possible.

Poland: Spotlight on Teachers

1. **Adapt Materials** – Simplify content for lower media competence, using visuals and practical examples.
2. **Diversify Methods** – Combine workshops, multimedia, group work, and discussions for engagement.
3. **Strengthen Analysis** – Prioritize **critical thinking** and awareness of manipulation tactics (e.g., fake news, deepfakes).
4. **Supportive Learning** – Create a relaxed, inclusive environment with clear,
5. **Qualified Trainers** – Train educators in **geragogy** for effective communication with older learners.
6. **Leverage Tools** – Use **smartphones, tablets, and fact-checking platforms** for hands-on learning.
7. **Monitor Progress** – Conduct **pre/post-training assessments** to improve effectiveness.
8. **AI Awareness** – Include modules on **generative AI risks** (e.g., deepfake manipulation).
9. **Universal Access** – Develop **scalable models** regardless of age or education level.

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3.3. Evaluation
Research Design

3.4. Intervention
Evaluation
Measurement

4. Unpacking the
Insights

4.1. Data Analysis

4.2. Ethical & Data
Protection
Guidance

5. Telling the Story

5.1. Reporting &
Dissemination

6. Continuous
Improvement &
Sustainability

7. Intervention
Evaluation
Recommendations

8. Useful Resources

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Section 8: Useful Resources

**Grab-and-Go Templates for
Media literacy and digital skills
intervention evaluation**

Useful Resource

A resource hub for advancing media literacy in education:

<https://media-and-learning.eu/category/subject/media-literacy>.

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Further Reading & Resources

- Tomczyk, Ł., Fedeli, L., Włoch, A., Limone, P., Frania, M., Guarini, P., Szyszka, M., Mascia, M. L., & Falkowska, J. (2022). Digital Competences of Pre-service Teachers in Italy and Poland. *Technology, Knowledge and Learning*, 28(2), 651–681. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10758-022-09626-6>
- Tomczyk, Ł. (2021). Declared and Real Level of Digital Skills of Future Teaching Staff. *Education Sciences*, 11(10), 619. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11100619>
- Tomczyk, Ł. (2023). Measuring digital competences. Ten common methodological challenges. *Problemy Opiekuńczo-Wychowawcze*, 620(5), 49–58. <https://doi.org/10.5604/01.3001.0053.6037>

Contact the REMEDIS Team

info@remedis-chanse.eu

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REMEDIS
Media Culture & Policy Lab
Parkstraat 45 box 3606
3000 Leuven – Belgium